

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

— on —

ENERGY, MATERIALS AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

(ICEMIT 2024)

December 19- 20, 2024 | Auditorium, Amity University Jharkhand

Abstract Book

Amity University Jharkhand Organizing...

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON ENERGY MATERIALS AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY (ICEMIT)

Supported by Anusandhan National Research Foundation (ANRF), Govt. of India
December 19th- 20th 2024, Hybrid Mode

Amity University Jharkhand

Amity University Jharkhand, Ranchi, is a private university located in Ranchi, Jharkhand, offers various undergraduate and postgraduate courses. Amity University Jharkhand is a part of 20-year-old, leading education group of India, Amity to revolutionize the Indian higher education Sector by providing globally benchmarked, research and employment-oriented education.

About Conference

The Main Objectives of the International Conference is to bring together Professionals, Academicians, Industry Experts, Researchers, Students and Enthusiasts to discuss various emerging trends and innovations, share research results and new directions in the field of next generation technologies.

Salient Features of the Conference

1. To offer Scopus indexed publication for the quality papers.
2. To listen from the national & international speakers from internationally acclaimed reputed organizations/ universities.
3. To get associated with the part of India's leading education group, Amity Education Group having two decades of excellence in education.
4. To provide a forum to exchange views, ideas & the latest innovations in the field of Material Science, Mechanical Engineering, Computer Science & Information Technology.
5. To offer learning on basics & advanced emerging trends & challenges in the field of Science and Technology.
6. Best Paper award (certificate) from each technical session of the conference.

THEMATIC AREAS: Tracks of ICEMIT 2024

Track 1: Advanced Materials Science and Applications

Track 2: Advanced Energy Technologies and Systems

Track 3: Emerging Trends in Information Technology and Its Application in Materials Science

DETAILS OF ICEMIT COMMITTEE MEMBERS

CONFERENCE STEERING COMMITTEE

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DR. ATUL CHAUHAN SIR

President, Ritnand Balved Education Foundation (RBEF); CEO, A K C Group of Companies & Hon'ble Chancellor, Amity University Jharkhand, Ranchi (India).

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Hon'ble Vice Chancellor

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Amity University Jharkhand, Ranchi

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Assistant Professor, Amity School of Engineering and Technology, Amity University Jharkhand, Ranchi

DR. ASHUTOSH SHARMA, Associate Professor, Amity Institute of Applied Sciences, Amity University Jharkhand, Ranchi

Message from Hon'ble Vice Chancellor

Dear Distinguished Delegates and Participants,

I am thrilled to announce Amity University Jharkhand's International Conference on Energy, Materials, and Information Technology (ICEMIT-2024), scheduled for December 19-20, 2024. As part of Asia's largest not-for-profit education conglomerate, Amity Education Group, we pride ourselves on excellence, boasting 200,000 students, 6,000 faculty members, and a global presence spanning 12 countries.

ICEMIT-2024 fosters interdisciplinary discussions, knowledge sharing, and cutting-edge research among scholars, professionals, and students. I commend the organizing committee for their dedication to curating this world-class academic gathering. This conference will inspire collaborations, driving transformative solutions to contemporary challenges.

I extend sincere gratitude to the Anusandhan National Research Foundation (ANRF), Government of India, for their invaluable support. I warmly welcome you to this enriching event, wishing ICEMIT-2024 immense success and fruitful outcomes benefiting society.

Thank you,

PROF. (DR.) ASHOK KUMAR SRIVASTAVA

Vice Chancellor

Amity University Jharkhand

Message from the Director's Desk

Progressive Research in Applied Science and Engineering are the upcoming and basic pillars of 21st Century. Continuous innovation and developments are required in this field for the development of the nation. Amity University Jharkhand, Ranchi has taken a step ahead by organizing an International Conference on Energy, Materials, and Information technology, supported by Anusandhan National Research Foundation (ANRF), Govt. of India on Challenges & Opportunities in Materials, Energy and Information Technology (ICEMIT- 2024).

I wish this International Conference a grand success, in achieving its objectives and striving for the best of this relatively new discipline. I would like to congratulate the members of organizing committee including the involved scholars & staffs of Amity University Jharkhand, Ranchi to conceptualize and conduct this conference.

Last but not the least; with your continued support and trust, I am sure that the efforts for making Amity University Jharkhand to reach the pinnacle of higher education would definitely be achieved.

Thank you.

PROF. (DR.) AJIT KUMAR PANDEY

Sr. Director & Dean (Academics)

Amity University Jharkhand, Ranchi

Message from the Registrar

I am delighted to learn that Amity University Jharkhand, Ranchi, is organizing the *International Conference on Energy, Materials, and Information Technology (ICEMIT-2024)*, supported by the Anusandhan National Research Foundation (ANRF), Government of India, scheduled for 19th and 20th December 2024.

This conference is a commendable effort to explore the challenges and opportunities in the fields of materials, energy, and information technology, providing a valuable platform for intellectual exchange among researchers, academicians, industry professionals, and students. Such initiatives reflect the university's commitment to fostering innovation and addressing contemporary issues.

Whereas the research is going on customization of materials for converting, transmitting, and storing more and more energy, the IT is enabling its optimization, and all together striving for the sustainable future.

I extend my heartfelt congratulations to the Convenors, Organizing Secretaries, and the entire organizing team for their meticulous planning and dedication in bringing this event to fruition. I am confident that the conference will yield meaningful discussions, inspire groundbreaking ideas, and contribute significantly to academic and research excellence.

As the Registrar of Amity University Jharkhand, I assure my full support for making this international conference a resounding success. My best wishes to all participants for a productive and enriching experience.

Thank You.

PRABHAKAR TRIPATHI

Registrar,

Amity University Jharkhand

Acknowledgement from the Convener

It is my immense pleasure to cordially invite you all to the “International Conference on Energy, Materials, and Information technology (ICEMIT-2024), supported by Anusandhan National Research Foundation (ANRF), Govt. of India, which will be held on 19th & 20th December’ 2024 at Amity University Jharkhand, Ranchi, India. The Conference is organized through Hybrid mode & aims to focus the attention of researchers and experts on various multidisciplinary fields of Energy, Materials and Information Technology providing opportunities for exchange of ideas, scientific knowledge and experience among researchers, academicians, scientists and students from different fields as well as from industry on the same platform for a brief yet intense period of discussion, collaboration, and addressing related problems in research and also to provide a platform to the researchers to showcase their talent and publish their work in reputed journals.

Eminent Invited Speakers will join us from various parts of the globe and hope everyone will learn emerging trends in biotechnology and enrich themselves. I wish you all the best of luck for the ICEMIT 2024.

Thank you

PROF. (DR.) JAYEETA CHATTOPADHYAY

Convener, ICEMIT- 2024

Professor, Amity Institute of Applied Sciences, Amity University Jharkhand, Ranchi.

DETAILS OF KEYNOTE AND INVITED TALK

Name	Affiliation	Title	Lecture
PROF. (DR.) JAE EK SON	Former President, Korea Institute of Energy Research, Daejon, S. Korea	Korean Energy Policy and The Status of International Energy Technology Market and R&D	Plenary Lecture
PROF. (DR.) AMIT BHATTACHARYA	Senior Principal Scientist, Central Salt & Marine Chemicals Research Institute, CSIR, Bhavnagar, Gujrat	Membranes – the trend in Water Purification	Plenary Lecture
DR. ANKIT PATEL	University of Minho, Portugal	How energy and information technology pave the way towards successful deployment of autonomous vehicles.	Plenary Lecture
PROF. (DR.) V. GANESH	Senior Principal Scientist, Central Electrochemical Research Institute, CSIR, Kodaikudi, Tamilnadu, India	Sustainable Electrochemical Conversion and Storage Solutions: Materials Electrochemistry Perspectives	Plenary Lecture
PROF. MANISH KUMAR	Professor, School of Physical Sciences, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, India	Novel hybrid halide perovskites based solar cells: The rise of perovskites photovoltaics.	Plenary Lecture
DR MUKESH JEWARIYA	Senior Scientist, CSIR-NPL New Delhi	Terahertz: A Future Prospects for New Era	Plenary Lecture
DR. VINAY KUMAR	Associate Professor, Savitribai Phule Pune University	Smart Nanomaterials for Combating Antimicrobial Resistance	Invited
DR. BASUDEV PRADHAN	Assistant Professor, Central University of Jharkhand	Next Generation Solar PV Technology	Invited

DR. ANIRBAN PRADHAN	BIT Mesra	Green and Renewable Hydrogen Fuel Production Based on Metal-Free Porous Carbon Materials	Invited
DR. BISWAJIT DEY	Assistant Professor, Visva-Bharati University	Functional Supramolecular Metallogel and Metallohydrogel	Invited
DR. ARCHANA DHASMANA	Himalaya school of Biosciences, Swami Rama Himalayan University	Sustainable Materials for Bio-Engineered Graft Fabrication	Invited
DR. NANDANI KUMARI	Scientist cum Co-ordinator, BAU	Artificial Intelligence in veterinary and other agri-allied sciences -scope, constraints and future prospect.	Invited
DR. PRATIBHAMOY DAS	IIT Patna	Advanced physics informed neural network algorithms for strongly coupled systems having boundary layers	Invited
DR. AVANISH KUMAR CHANDAN	Senior Scientist, CSIR-National Metallurgical Laboratory, Jamshedpur	Warm rolling-based microstructural engineering to overcome the strength-ductility trade-off in a medium manganese steel	Invited

Details of Abstracts for ICEMIT 2024

Track 1: Advanced Materials Science and Applications			
Abstract No.	Registered Authors	Category	Title of Abstract
ICEMIT-MAT103	Binay Prakash Akhouri Rajeev Ranjan Deo Pandey	Oral	Equations of State Method for Contact Angle Interpretation
ICEMIT-MAT105	Prithwi Raj Nayak Binay Prakash Akhouri	Oral	Study of Virial Coefficients of Polymer Solutions: Osmotic Pressure
ICEMIT-MAT106	Sudhir Kumar Dr. Rajeev Ranjan	Oral	Impact of Vibration on Weld Quality, Properties and Microstructure in Vibration Assisted Tungsten Inert Gas (TIG) Welding: A Review
ICEMIT-MAT107	Sudhir Kumar Dr. Rajeev Ranjan	Oral	A Review on Recent Advancement in Gas Tungsten Arc Welding (GTAW)
ICEMIT-MAT112	S. Denamsetti, N. Mandal, R.D.S Nishanth	Oral	Revolutionizing Medical Education and Research: The Role of Virtual Dissection Tables in Biomaterial Evaluation
ICEMIT-MAT115	Chandan Kumar, Vivek Chaudhary, Zahid Ali Ansari, Paramveer Kumar, Saurabh Priyadarshi	Oral	Thermal Buoyancy-Driven Vortex Shedding Behind a Porous Circular Cylinder at Low Reynolds Numbers
ICEMIT-MAT118	Sandhya Kumari, Prabin Kumar Mahato, Prashanta Patra, Swarat Chaudhuri, Saroj Kumar Singh	Oral	Development of Eco-Friendly Corrosion and Wear Resistant Ni-Graphene Nano-Composite Coating via Electroless Deposition Technique for Mild Steel Substrate
ICEMIT-MAT125	Sona Kumari, Shweta Sinha, S.K. Sinha, R.K. Chaudhary	Oral	Impact on Dielectric Properties of Gd ²⁺ Modified Lead Titanate Nanoceramics Prepared by High Energy Ball Milling Method
ICEMIT-MAT127	Kamalika Tiwari, Subhasis Datta, Santigopal Pain	Oral	Metal-Oxide Modified Electrode for Floral Identification of Honey Using Electronic Tongue
ICEMIT-MAT130	Aditya Kushwaha, Shalini Vardhan, Pradeep Kumar, Neeraj Goel	Oral	Ion Beam Deposition of Ag Nanoclusters on MoTe ₂ : A Computational Study of NO ₂ Sensing
ICEMIT-MAT131	Pradeep Kumar, Ruchi, Michael Augustine Arockiyadoss	Oral	Efficient Helmet Detection Based on YOLO-V7 for Real-Time Safety and Monitoring System
ICEMIT-MAT132	Ankita Yadav, Mukesh Kumar, Ashutosh Sharma	Oral	Synthesis and Characterization of Hexagonal Boron Nitride for Gas Sensing Applications

ICEMIT-MAT134	Shalini Mehta, Smita Lata, Shreya Ranjan, Jutishna Bora, Sumira Malik, Sarvesh Rustagi, Nayan Talukdar, Seema Ramniwas	Oral	Genotoxic and Cytotoxic effect of Bleaching powder on living cell
ICEMIT-MAT135	Sagar Mondal, Swati Priya, Sumira Malik, Smita Lata, Survesh Rustogi, Ravi K. Deshwal, Seema Ramniwas, Jutishna Bora	Oral	The future of nutraceuticals in Diabetes Management
ICEMIT-MAT136	Subhajit Nan, Anushka Ghoshal, Swati Priya, Sagar Mondal, Smita Lata, Indrani Barman, Jutishna Bora, Sumira Malik, Sarvesh Rustagi, Nayan Talukdar, Seema Ramniwas	Oral	A perspective review on Interlinkage between Polycystic Ovary Syndrome and Diabetes Mellitus
ICEMIT-MAT138	Binay Prakash Akhouri, Rajeev Ranjan Deo Pandey	Oral	Study of axis symmetric shapes of sessile drops
ICEMIT-MAT139	Dr. Richa Mishra, Dr. Dhananjay K. Pandey	Oral	Advances in the Synthesis and Bioactivity of Fused N & O-Heterocycles: Microwave-assisted Multicomponent Reactions
ICEMIT-MAT140	Dr. Amit Kumar Dutta, Ms. Surbhi Kumari	Oral	Various Revolutionized Nanoparticles Targeting the Bcr-Abl Genes in Chronic Myeloid Leukemia Patients
ICEMIT-MAT141	Honey Nishad, Sweta Kumari, Srija Bhattacharya, Dr. Smita Lata, Dr. Sumira Malik, Nayan Talukdar, Dr. Jutishna Bora	Oral	Risk factors associated with the development of Diabetes in Women
ICEMIT-MAT142	Srija Bhattacharya, Honey Nishad, Dr. Amit Kumar Dutta	Oral	Sickle Cell Anaemia: A Report on Neglected Chronic Disease of Increasing Global Health Importance
ICEMIT-MAT144	Dr. Sarika M Jagtap, Ms. Rasika M Chandramore, Mr. Bhushankumar N Shinde, Mr. V R. Sonawane, Ms. T. S. Deshmukh	Oral	Design And Development of Robotic System for Welding Operation Using Soldering Gun on Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS) Material
ICEMIT-MAT145	Mayank Srivastava, Divya Srivastava, Biresh Kumar, Rahul Singh, Rajeev Ranjan, Pravin Singh, Richa Sinha	Oral	CFD-Based Study on the Thermal Performance of Encapsulated Phase Change Materials in Energy Storage

Track 2: Advanced Energy Technologies and Systems

Abstract No.	Registered Authors	Category	Title of Abstract
ICEMIT EN101	Pinaki Mukherjee	Oral	Energy saving by using Heat Pump
ICEMIT EN103	Bhupali Kumbhar, Ranjeet Khandekar, Pravin Gavade	Oral	Analyzing Range of an EV for Different Driving Cycles under Specific State of Charge Scenarios
ICEMIT EN106	Roquia Perween, Binay Prakash Akhouri	Oral	Equation of state and excess energy for size asymmetric square well mixtures
ICEMIT EN109	Jinsha Shereef, Uma Krishnakumar, Fathima Farhin M M, Gayathri Anil, Gayathri J Menon	Oral	Enhanced Bioethanol Production Using LCB
ICEMIT EN110	Nikhil Jayaraj	Oral	Regulatory Framework and Consumer Protection: Policy Impacts on End Users in Solar Energy Storage Adoption
ICEMIT EN113	Subhajit Roy, K. Pavan Kumar, Dulal Chandra Das, Nidul Sinha	Oral	Assessing the Cybersecurity Challenges in Virtual Power Plants Through Review of Risks and Resilience Strategies
ICEMIT EN115	E. Nirmala Devi, M. Sreenivasa Rao, G. Rama Krishna, T. Jayanand Kumar, P. Mahesh Sai venkat	Oral	Improvement of Engine Performance Emission and Combustion Characteristics of Mahua biodiesel fuelled in constant speed CI Engine using FeCl ₃ nanoparticle
ICEMIT EN116	Rudra Moorthi Ravindran, Deeparanjini Rajakumar, Vaishnavi Vadivelu, Prakash Nachimuthu, Parthasarathy Karthikeyan	Oral	Innovative Approaches to Electrifying Transportation Systems: Challenges and Opportunities
ICEMIT EN119	Durga Prasad Saini, Kalpana Meena	Oral	Enhancing Grid Stability: Fault Ride-Through Protection for Motor-Generator Pair Systems in Renewable Energy
ICEMIT EN122	Prabhakar Tripathi a, Mukund Chandra Mehta, Kasturi Sahay	Oral	Assessment of Barriers and Challenges in Undertaking Green Entrepreneurship and Green Market
ICEMIT EN123	Ankur Aggrawal, Dr. Rahul Singh, Dr. Mayank Srivastava, Dr. Sunny Chandra, Dr. Shiv Kumar Ray, Dr. Ramprit Baitha, Pankaj Singh	Oral	Application of Rayleigh Distribution for Micro-Wind Turbine Prediction: A Case Study on Wind Energy Potential in Gorakhpur District at 10 m height
ICEMIT EN124	Ankur Aggrawal, Dr. Rahul Singh, Dr. Mayank Srivastava, Dr. Sunny Chandra, Dr. Shiv Kumar Ray, Dr. Ramprit Baitha, Pankaj Singh	Oral	Application of Weibull Distribution for Micro-Wind Turbine Prediction: A Case Study on Wind Energy Potential in Jaisalmer District at 10 m height
ICEMIT EN125	Mayank Srivastava, Rahul Singh, Richa Sinha, Pranav Kumar Singh	Oral	The Design Innovation and technological Advances in Pumped Hydro Storage System

ICEMIT EN126	Shashwat Gupta, Saurabh Kumar, Ashutosh Choubey, Dr. Mayank	Oral	Global Potential of Renewable Energy Sources: A Literature Assessment
ICEMIT-EN127	Rajnish Kumar, Om Prakash, Rahul Kumar, Alok Kumar, Pallavi Sindhu	Oral	Comparative analysis of bioethanol production yield between pre-treated and untreated rice-straw

Track 3: Emerging Trends in Information Technology and Its Application in Materials Science

Abstract No.	Registered Authors	Category	Title of Abstract
ICEMIT IT101	Pankaj Kumar, Bimal Kumar Mishra, Pankaj Rai	Oral	Attack Detection in Camera and Lidar in Smart Cars Using Time Delay Differential Equations
ICEMIT IT104	Ritesh Kumar Pathak, Raj Kumar Singh, Kumari Mamta, Kali Krishna Giri	Oral	RT Duroid dielectric material-based design and simulation of medium gain patch antenna for Sub-urban areas wireless communication
ICEMIT IT110	Divya Sri Chennupati, Mahammad Firose Shaik, Pinnamaneni Nandini, Bommakani Siva Ganesh, Polluri Manasa	Oral	Anesthesia Dosage Prediction: A Deep Learning Approach for Enhanced Patient Care
ICEMIT IT111	Dharshne Manoharan, Vaishnavi Vadivelu, Janani Nallamuthu, Kanishka Gopinath, Prakash Nachimuthu	Oral	Smart Solutions: Leveraging AI and Machine Learning in Tourism and Financial Sectors
ICEMIT IT112	Vaishnavi Vadivelu, Pavidhra Veni Veerabagu, Sowmya Rajamani, Prakash Nachimuthu, Parthasarathy Karthikeyan	Oral	Smart industries: Leveraging IoT and Edge computing for innovation in healthcare and tourism sectors
ICEMIT IT113	Kunal Kumar, Arun Kumar Malaisamy, Kunal Ranjan, Sonam Kumari, Rajani Sharma	Oral	AI Based detection of phytochemicals regulating Cholesterol Level
ICEMIT IT115	Prakash Nachimuthu, Arunikasri Mahadevan, Kishore Kanagasabapathi, Parthasarathy Karthikeyan, Vaishnavi Vadivelu	Oral	Transparency and Efficiency: Blockchain for Modern Supply Chain Management
ICEMIT IT117	Shruti Sharma, Maira Khalid, Ashutosh Sharma, Wonsik Yoon	Oral	Deep Reinforcement Learning for Resource Optimization in UAV-Enabled Wireless Networks
ICEMIT IT119	Abhishek Kumar, Upendra Kumar, Rajesh K Tiwari	Oral	AI-Powered Customer Profiling and Segmentation to Reduce Booking Cancellations
ICEMIT IT123	Bires Kumar, Sanyam Anand, Purushottam Kumar, Mayank Srivastava, Ramkrishn Prajapati, Manorama Patnaik	Oral	Molecular Pathogenesis and Epidemiological Dynamics of Cervical Neoplasia: Advances in Precision Diagnostics and Multimodal Therapeutics

ICEMIT IT127	Akanksha Malakar, Aditya Kumar, Nisha Singh, Sonali Vyas	Oral	Thermal Imaging and Machine Learning: Enhancing Night-time Pedestrian Detection for Autonomous Vehicles
ICEMIT IT129	Anurag Sinha, Biresh Kumar, Anita Kumar, Abhishek Kumar, Vineet Kumar Singh, Binod Kumar Sharma	Oral	Intelligent Biodegradable Materials Composite Packaging (IBCP): An Integrated IoT-ML-LLM Approach for Sustainable Design, Tracking, and Waste Management
ICEMIT IT131	Kavita Maithani	Oral	Importance of Information Technology in Education in Uttarakhand
ICEMIT IT132	Agnes Nalini Vincent, K. Sakthidasan, Uhoze Bagurubumwe	Oral	Improving Accuracy of Marine Data Prediction using Hyper Parameters Optimisation of Hybrid Deep RNN
ICEMIT IT133	Pavan DS, Ronak R Jain, Tirthankar Karmakar, Ashwini S Savanth, Jyoti R Munavalli	Oral	Analysis of Remote Voting System Mechanism
ICEMIT IT134	Puneet Misra, Arun Singh Yadav	Oral	A Novel Multi-Estimator Framework for Sequential Forward Feature Selection in Cancer Prediction
ICEMIT IT135	Kunal Kumar, Rahul Kumar Singh	Oral	Combining Mathematical Epidemiology and Machine Learning for Disease Spread Analysis

CONFERENCE SCHEDULE

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON ENERGY, MATERIALS AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY (December 19 – 20, 2024)

Day 1: 19th December 2024

Registration: 9:00 AM – 10:00 AM

INAUGURAL SESSION: 10:00 AM – 10:30 AM

Session 1: 10:30 AM – 01:20 PM; Venue: Auditorium

Plenary Lecture – I
10:30 AM – 11:10 AM

PROF. (DR.) JAE EK SON, Former President, Korea Institute of Energy Research, Daejon, S. Korea
Title: Korean Energy Policy and The Status of International Energy Technology Market and R&D

HIGH TEA: 11:10 AM – 11:40 AM

Plenary Lecture – II
11:40 AM – 12:20 PM

PROF. (DR.) AMIT BHATTACHARYA, Senior Principal Scientist, Central Salt and Marine Chemical Research Institute, CSIR, Bhavnagar, Gujrat, India
Title: Membranes – The Trend in Water Purification

SESSION CHAIR

PROF. (DR.) JAE EK SON, Former President, Korea Institute of Energy Research, Daejon, S. Korea

PROF. (DR.) AMIT BHATTACHARYA, Senior Principal Scientist, Central Salt and Marine Chemical Research Institute, CSIR, Bhavnagar, Gujrat, India

Invited Talk – I
12:20 PM – 12:40 PM

DR. BISWAJIT DEY, Assistant Professor, Visva-Bharati University, West Bengal
Title: Functional Supramolecular Metallogel and Metallohydrogel

INVITED TALK – II
12:40 PM – 01:00 PM

DR. PRATIBHAMOY DAS, Assistant Professor, Indian Institute of Technology, Patna, India
Title: Advanced physics informed neural network algorithms for strongly coupled systems having boundary layers

01:00 PM – 01:10 PM

Design And Development of Robotic System for Welding Operation Using Soldering Gun on Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS) Material-MAT 144 |
MS. RASIKA M. CHANDRAMORE; jagtap.sarika@kbtcoe.org

01:10 PM – 01:20 PM

Revolutionizing Medical Education and Research: The Role of Virtual Dissection Tables in Biomaterial Evaluation MAT112 | **DR. R.D.S. NISHANTH**; sam.nishanth@immersivelabz.com

LUNCH BREAK: 01:20 PM – 02:10 PM

Session 2 (A): 02:10 PM – 05:10 PM; Venue: Seminar Hall

SESSION CHAIR	DR. RAHUL , Associate Professor, Amity University Jharkhand DR. SUMIRA MALIK , Associate Professor, Amity University Jharkhand
Invited Talk – III 02:10 PM – 02:30 PM	DR. VINAY KUMAR , Associate Professor, Savitribai Phule Pune University Title: Smart Nanomaterials for Combating Antimicrobial Resistance
Invited Talk – IV 02:30 PM – 02:50 PM	Dr. Basudev Pradhan , Assistant Professor, Central University of Jharkhand Title: Next Generation Solar PV Technology
02:50 PM – 03:00 PM	Study of Virial Coefficients of Polymer Solutions: Osmotic Pressure. - MAT105 MR. PRITHWI RAJ NAYAK ; prithwiraj336@gmail.com
03:00 PM – 03:10 PM	Enhancing Grid Stability: Fault Ride-Through Protection for Motor-Generator Pair Systems in Renewable Energy- EN119 MR. DURGA PRASAD SAINI ; dpsaini.saini05@gmail.com
03:10 PM – 03:20 PM	Enhanced Bioethanol Production using Lignocellulosic Biomass- EN109 MS. JINSHA SHEREEF ; jinshashereef@gmail.com
03:20 PM – 03:30 PM	Assessing the Cybersecurity Challenges in Virtual Power Plants Through Review of Risks and Resilience Strategies - EN113 MR. SUBHAJIT ROY ; subhajitroy111@gmail.com
03:30 PM – 03:40 PM	Various Revolutionized Nanoparticles Targeting the BCR-ABL Genes in Chronic Myeloid Leukemia Patients- MAT140 DR. AMIT KUMAR DUTTA ; drakdutta81@gmail.com
TEA BREAK: 03:40 PM – 04:00 PM	
Invited Talk – V 04:00 PM – 04:20 PM	DR. ANIRBAN PRADHAN , Assistant Professor, Birla Institute of Technology, Mesra Title: Green and Renewable Hydrogen Fuel Production based on Metal Free Porous Carbon Materials
04:20 PM – 04:30 PM	Improvement of Engine Performance Emission and Combustion Characteristics of Mahua biodiesel fueled in constant speed CI Engine using FeCl ₃ nanoparticle. - EN115 DR. E NIRMALA DEVI ; enirmala@giet.ac.in
04:30 PM – 04:40 PM	Analyzing EV Range for Different Driving Cycles under Specific State of Charge Scenarios - EN-103 MR. BHUPALI POPAT KUMBHAR ; bhupali.k887@gmail.com
Invited Talk – VI 04:40 PM – 05:00 PM	Dr. Avanish Chandan , Senior Scientist, CSIR-National Metallurgical Laboratory, Jamshedpur Title: Warm rolling-based microstructural engineering to overcome the strength-ductility trade-off in a medium manganese steel
05:00 PM – 05:10 PM	Equations of State Method for Contact Angle Interpretation- MAT103 RAJEEV RANJAN DEO PANDEY ; rrdeoo@gmail.com
05:10 PM – 05:20 PM	Study of axis symmetric shapes of sessile drops- MAT138 RAJEEV RANJAN DEO PANDEY ; rrdeoo@gmail.com
05:20 PM – 05:30 PM	CFD-BASED STUDY ON THE THERMAL PERFORMANCE OF ENCAPSULATED PHASE CHANGE MATERIALS IN ENERGY STORAGE – MAT145 DR. MAYANK SRIVASTAVA ; msrivastava@rnc.amity.edu

Session 2 (B): 02:10 PM – 05:10 PM; Venue: Lecture Hall 245

SESSION CHAIR	DR. SOUMEN KANRAR , Associate Professor, Amity University Jharkhand DR. ASUTOSH SHARMA , Associate Professor, Amity University Jharkhand
Invited Talk – VI 02:10 PM – 02:30 PM	DR. ARCHANA DHASMANA , Assistant Professor, Himalaya School of Biosciences, Swami Rama Himalayan University Title: Sustainable Materials for Bio-Engineered Graft Fabrication
02:30 PM – 02:40 PM	Thermal bouncy-driven vortex shedding behind a porous circular cylinder at low Reynolds number. - MAT115 DR. CHANDAN KUMAR ; cksingh158@gmail.com
02:40 PM – 02:50 PM	Impact of Vibration on Weld Quality, Properties and Microstructure in Vibration Assisted Tungsten Inert Gas (TIG) Welding- A Review - MAT106 MR. SUDHIR KUMAR ; sudhir02kr@gmail.com
02:50 PM – 03:00 PM	Ion Beam Deposition of Ag Nanoclusters on MoTe ₂ : A Computational Study of NO ₂ Sensing- MAT130 MR. ADITYA KUSHWAHA ; aditya.kushwaha.phd21@nsut.ac.in
03:00 PM – 03:10 PM	Equation of state and excess energy for size asymmetric square well mixture. - EN106 MS. ROQUIA PERWEEN ; rasoolroquia@gmail.com
03:10 PM – 03:20 PM	Intelligent Biodegradable Materials Composite Packaging (IBCP): An Integrated IoT-ML-LLM Approach for Sustainable Design, Tracking, and Waste Management IT129 MR. ANURAG SINHA ; anuragsinha257@gmail.com
Invited Talk – VII 03:20 PM – 03:40 PM	DR. NANDANI KUMARI , Assistant Professor, Birsa Agricultural University, Ranchi Title: Artificial Intelligence in veterinary and other Agri-allied sciences -scope, constraints and future prospect
TEA BREAK: 03:40 PM – 04:00 PM	
04:00 PM – 04:10 PM	Anesthesia dosage prediction: A deep learning approach for enhanced patient care- IT110 MS. DIVYA SRI CHENNUPATI ; chennupatidivyasri1295@gmail.com
04:10 PM – 04:20 PM	Transparency and Efficiency: Blockchain for Modern Supply Chain Management- IT115 ARUNIKASRI MAHADEVAN ; vaishnacsca@gmail.com
04:20 PM – 04:30 PM	Molecular Pathogenesis and Epidemiological Dynamics of Cervical Neoplasia: Advances in Precision Diagnostics and Multimodal Therapeutics - IT123 MR. SANYAM ANAND ; bkumar@rnc.amity.edu
04:30 PM – 04:40 PM	Combining Mathematical Epidemiology and Machine Learning for Disease Spread Analysis- IT135 MR. KUNAL KUMAR ; rahul282828@gmail.com
04:40 PM – 04:50 PM	A Novel Multi-Estimator Framework for Sequential Forward Feature Selection in Cancer Prediction- IT134 MR. ARUN SINGH YADAV ; arun.ai.lkouniv@gmail.com

Day 2: 20th December 2024

Session 3: 09:00 AM – 12:40 PM; Venue: Auditorium

Plenary Lecture – III 09:00 AM – 09:40 AM	DR. ANKIT PATEL , University of Minho, Portugal
Plenary Lecture – IV 09:40 AM – 10:20 AM	PROF. (DR.) V. GANESH , Senior Principal Scientist, Central Electrochemical Research Institute, CSIR, Karaikudi, Tamilnadu Title: Sustainable Electrochemical Conversion and Storage Solutions: Materials Electrochemistry Perspectives
Plenary Lecture – V 10:20 AM – 11:00 AM	PROF. (DR.) MANISH KUMAR , Professor, School of Physical Sciences, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, IN Title: Novel hybrid halide perovskites based solar cells: The rise of perovskites photovoltaics
SESSION CHAIR	PROF. (DR.) V. GANESH , Senior Principal Scientist, Central Electrochemical Research Institute, CSIR, Karaikudi, Tamilnadu, IN PROF. (DR.) MANISH KUMAR , Professor, School of Physical Sciences, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi, IN

High Tea: 11:00 AM – 11:30 AM

11:30 AM – 11:45 AM	Energy saving by using Heat Pump - EN 101 MR. PINAKI MUKHERJEE ; pinaki69@gmail.com
11:45 AM – 11:55 AM	Application of Rayleigh Distribution for Micro-Wind Turbine Prediction: A Case Study on Wind Energy Potential in Gorakhpur District at 10m height- EN123 MR. ANKUR AGRAWAL ; rahul282828@gmail.com
11:55 AM – 12:05 PM	Synthesis and Characterization of Hexagonal Boron Nitride for Gas Sensing Applications- MAT132 MS. ANKITA YADAV ; ashu.materials@gmail.com
12:05 PM – 12:15 PM	Application of Weibull Distribution for Micro-Wind Turbine Prediction: A Case Study on Wind Energy Potential in Jaisalmer District at 10m height- EN-124 MR. ANKUR AGRAWAL ; rahul282828@gmail.com
12:15 PM – 12:25 PM	A Review on Recent Advancement in Gas Tungsten Arc Welding (GTAW)- MAT107 SUDHIR KUMAR ; sudhir02kr@gmail.com
12:25 PM – 12:35 PM	Metal-Oxide Modified Electrode for Floral Identification of Honey Using Electronic Tongue- MAT127 DR KAMALIKA TIWARI ; kamalika.tiwari@bcrec.ac.in
12:35 PM – 12:45 PM	Innovative Approaches to Electrifying Transportation Systems: Challenges and Opportunities- EN116 MR. RUDRA MOORTHY RAVINDRAN , vaishnacsca@gmail.com
12:45 PM – 12:55 PM	Development of eco-friendly corrosion and wear resistant Ni-graphene nano-composite coating via electroless deposition technique for mild steel substrate MAT-118 MS. SANDHAYA KUMARI ; ku_sandhaya@yahoo.com
Plenary Lecture – VI 12:55 PM – 01:35 PM	DR MUKESH JEWARIYA , Senior Scientist, CSIR-National Physical Laboratory, New Delhi Title: Terahertz: A Future Prospects for New Era

LUNCH BREAK: 01:35 PM – 02:30 PM

Session 4 (A): 02:30 PM – 03:40 PM; Venue: Seminar Hall

SESSION CHAIR	DR. ANKIT PATEL , University of Minho, Portugal DR. SOUMEN KANRAR , Associate Professor, Amity University Jharkhand
02:30 PM – 02:40 PM	Attack Detection in Camera and Lidar in Smart Cars Using Time Delay Differential Equations - IT101 MR. PANKAJ KUMAR ; pankajunav@gmail.com
02:40 PM – 02:50 PM	RT Duroid dielectric material-based design and simulation of medium gain patch antenna for Sub-urban areas wireless communication- IT 104 MR. RITESH KUMAR PATHAK ; kumarriteshx@gmail.com
02:50 PM – 03:00 PM	Importance of information technology in education in Uttarakhand- IT131 MS. KAVITA MAITHANI ; kavimaithani92@gmail.com
03:00 PM – 03:10 PM	Thermal Imaging and Machine Learning: Enhancing Night-time Pedestrian Detection for Autonomous Vehicles- IT127 MS. AKANKSHA MALAKAR ; akankshamalakar@gmail.com
03:10 PM – 03:20 PM	Improving Accuracy of Marine Data Prediction using Hyper Parameters Optimisation of Hybrid Deep RNN- IT132 MRS. AGNES NALINI VINCENT ; vanalini@mauritius.amity.edu
03:20 PM – 03:30 PM	Analysis of Remote Voting System Mechanism- IT133 MR. TIRTHANKAR KARMAKAR ; tirthankarkarmakar259@gmail.com
03:30 PM – 03:40 PM	Regulatory Framework and Consumer Protection: Policy Impacts on End Users in Solar Energy Storage Adoption-EN110 DR. NIKHIL JAYARAJ ; nikhil.jayaraj@postgrad.curtin.edu.au
03:40 PM – 03:50 PM	Global Potential of Renewable Energy Sources: A Literature Assessment - EN126 MR. SAURABH KUMAR ; guptashashwat936@gmail.com

TEA BREAK: 03:50 PM – 04:00 PM

Session 4 (B): 02:30 PM – 03:40 PM; Venue: Lecture Hall 245

SESSION CHAIR	DR. POOJA JHA , Associate Professor, Amity University Jharkhand DR. NARENDRA KUMAR , Associate Professor, Amity University Jharkhand
02:30 PM – 02:40 PM	Smart industries: Leveraging IoT and Edge computing for innovation in healthcare and tourism sectors- IT112 MS. SOWMYA RAJAMANI ; vaishnacsca@gmail.com
02:40 PM – 02:50 PM	AI Based detection of phytochemicals regulating Cholesterol Level - IT113 DR. RAJANI SHARMA ; rsharma@nc.amity.edu
02:50 PM – 03:00 PM	Smart solutions: leveraging ai and machine learning in tourism and financial sectors- IT111 JANANI NALLAMUTHU ; vaishnacsca@gmail.com
03:00 PM – 03:10 PM	Risk factors associated with the development of Diabetes in Women. - MAT141 HONEY NISHAD ; honeynishad6916@gmail.com
03:10 PM – 03:20 PM	The future of nutraceuticals in Diabetes Management- MAT135 SAGAR MONDAL ; sagar.mondal@s.amity.edu
03:20 PM – 03:30 PM	Sickle Cell Anaemia: A Report on Neglected Chronic Disease of Increasing Global Health Importance- MAT142 SRIJA BHATTACHARYA ; srija.b.0203@gmail.com
03:30 PM – 03:40 PM	Genotoxic and Cytotoxic effect of Bleaching powder on living cell- MAT134 MS. SHREYA RANJAN ; rakeshshreya987@gmail.com
03:40 PM – 03:50 PM	A perspective review on Interlinkage between Polycystic Ovary Syndrome and Diabetes Mellitus MAT-136 MS ROSHNI JHA ; roshnijha538@gmail.com

TEA BREAK: 03:50 PM – 04:00 PM

Session 4 (C): 02:30 PM – 04:30 PM; Venue: Lecture Hall 246	
SESSION CHAIR	DR. BIRESH KUMAR , Associate Professor, Amity University Jharkhand DR. MAYANK SRIVASTAVA , Assistant Professor, Amity University Jharkhand
02:30 PM – 02:40 PM	Efficient Helmet Detection Based on YOLO-V7 for Real-Time- MAT131 MS. RUCHI pradeeprohilla70@gmail.com
02:40 PM – 02:50 PM	Forecasting Hospital Readmission Rates in the U.S. Using Time-Series Analysis and Machine Learning Models IT-136 MD SHOAB ALAM ; bkumar@rnc.amity.edu
02:50 PM – 03:00 PM	Advances in the Synthesis and Bioactivity of Fused Pyrans: Microwave-Assisted Multicomponent Reactions MAT-139 DR. RICHA MISHRA ; dkpandey@rnc.amity.edu
03:00 PM – 03:10 PM	AI-Powered Customer Profiling and Segmentation to Reduce Booking Cancellations IT-119 ABHISHEK KUMAR ; bkumar@rnc.amity.edu
03:10 PM – 03:20 PM	Deep Reinforcement Learning for Resource Optimization in UAV-Enabled Wireless Networks IT-117 MS. MAIRA KHALID ; shruti@ajou.ac.kr
03:20 PM – 03:30 PM	The design innovation and technological advances in pumped hydro storage system EN-125 MR PRANAV KUMAR SINGH ; pranavrajput13121929@gmail.com
03:30 PM – 03:40 PM	Comparative analysis of bioethanol production yield between pre-treated and untreated rice-straw EN-127 DR. RAHUL ; rahul282828@gmail.com
03.40 PM-03.50 PM	Impact on dielectric properties of gd+2 modified lead titanate nanoceramics prepared by high energy ball milling method- MAT125 MS. SONA KUMARI ; sweta.sinha2203@gmail.com
03.50 PM-04.00 PM	Intelligent Biodegradable Materials Composite Packaging (IBCP): An Integrated IoT-ML-LLM Approach for Sustainable Design, Tracking, and Waste Management – IT129 ANURAG SINHA ; anuragsinha257@gmail.com
04.00 PM-04.10 PM	Assessment of Barriers and Challenges in Undertaking Green Entrepreneurship and Green Market – EN122 PRABHAKAR TRIPATHI ; registrar@rnc.amity.edu
04.10 PM-04.20 PM	Evaluation and Mechanical characterization of basalt fibre reinforced biodegradable based PLA composites: A computational approach – MAT119 PRIYA TIWARI , jmkhare2010@rediffmail.com
04.20 PM-04.30 PM	An improved SAFT-type equation of state for variable –range square-well chain fluids – EN120 ROQUIA PERWEEN , rasoolroquia@gmail.com
TEA BREAK: 04:30 PM – 04:40 PM	
Valedictory Session: 04:00 PM – 05:30 PM; VENUE: AUDITORIUM	
04:00 PM – 04:10 PM	Valedictory Report
Plenary Lecture - VIII 04:10 PM – 04:40 PM	PROF. (DR.) RATAN KR. DEY , Professor, Central University of Jharkhand, Ranchi
04:40 PM – 05:20 PM	Certificate Distribution
05:20 PM - 05:25 PM	Address by Hon'ble Vice-Chancellor
05:25 PM – 05:30 PM	Concluding Remarks and Vote of Thanks

PLENARY SESSIONS

Plenary Lecture 1

Korean Energy Policy and The Status of International Energy Technology Market and R&D

Prof. (Dr.) Jae Ek Son

Former President, Korea Institute of Energy Research, Daejeon, South Korea

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South Korea's energy policies during the Yoon administration are intended to meet global energy concerns, carbon neutrality, and economic growth while improving energy security and policy acceptability. These policies are consistent with the First National Framework Plan for Carbon Neutrality and Green Growth and the Eleventh Basic Plan for Power Supply and Demand (2024-2038). The administration is focused on redefining the energy mix in a viable manner, building strong resource and energy security, improving energy efficiency, and promoting emerging green sectors as export drivers. Key activities include renewable energy expansion plans, supply chain strengthening, and the implementation of the Special Act on the Promotion of Distributed Energy, which facilitates the transition to a distributed energy system through legislative frameworks and enhanced distribution management. The first National Strategic Technology Nurture Plan includes vital technologies for energy independence and prosperity. The administration also focuses on fulfilling the 2030 Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC) objectives by revising sector-specific reduction milestones and

allocating financial resources for policy implementation. These programs aim to build a sustainable, resilient, and export-oriented energy ecosystem, furthering South Korea's leadership in green growth and carbon neutrality.

Keywords: Energy policy, carbon, Korea, economy, green growth

Plenary Lecture 2

Membranes – the trend in Water Purification

Prof. (Dr.) Amit Bhattacharya

Membrane Science and Separation Technology Division, Council of Scientific & Industrial Research-Central Salt and Marine Chemicals Research Institute (CSIR-CSMCRI), Bhavnagar-364002 Gujarat, India. †Academy of Scientific and Innovative Research, Council of Scientific & Industrial Research -Central Salt and Marine Chemicals Research Institute (CSIR-CSMCRI), Bhavnagar-364002, Gujarat, India.

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Membrane development is a dynamic process that moves forward slowly, and recommendations are made based on the best science available. The history of reverse osmosis began in the 1950s. Srinivasa Sourirajan and Sidney Loeb prepared an asymmetric cellulose acetate membrane capable of desalting the seawater through a pressure-driven technique. As cellulose acetate membrane

is natural, it has some limitations in chemical and mechanical stabilities.

Considering the limitations, the research was directed to find different membranes from synthetic materials (viz. polysulfone, polyethersulfone, polyvinylidene fluoride, polyvinyl alcohol). All the membranes have their limitations. To search for the better one, John Cadotte from Midwest Research Institute in the 1970s succeeded in polyamide composite membranes. The composite is the path-finding solution that overcomes the limitations of asymmetric cellulose acetate membrane in separation science. It is a three-layer composite. The polyamide is formed on the asymmetric support layer, which is supported by nonwoven polyester fabric. It is formed through the interfacial polymerisation of aromatic diamine and trifunctional acid chloride. The interfacial polymerization reaction is the controlling medium in which one can add different moieties to influence the membrane properties. Researchers from various disciplines have orchestrated the membrane development dynamics.

Keywords: Cellulose, composite, membrane, polyamide, fabric, separation

Plenary Lecture 3

Dr. Ankit Patel

University of Minho, Portugal

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The deployment of autonomous vehicles (AVs) represents a transformative shift in modern transportation, driven by advances in energy systems and information technology. This talk explores the interplay between these two domains and their role in enabling the widespread adoption of AVs.

On the energy front, innovations in battery technologies, charging infrastructure, and energy-efficient designs ensure that AVs meet the demands of sustainable mobility. Meanwhile, breakthroughs in information technology, including artificial intelligence, edge computing, and high-speed communication networks, empower AVs with real-time decision-making, precise navigation, and robust safety mechanisms. By integrating energy and IT systems, the talk highlights solutions for overcoming critical challenges such as range anxiety, infrastructure scalability, data security, and system reliability. It concludes by addressing the potential of these technologies to shape an ecosystem where AVs contribute to safer, greener, and more efficient transportation systems.

Keywords: Autonomous vehicles, energy, information technology, artificial intelligence, safety.

Plenary Lecture 4

Sustainable Electrochemical Conversion and Storage Solutions: Materials Electrochemistry Perspectives

Prof. (Dr.) V. Ganesh

Electrodeics and Electrocatalysis (EEC) Division, CSIR – Central Electrochemical Research Institute (CSIR – CECRI), Karaikudi – 630003, Tamil Nadu, India.

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Ever increasing climate calamities along with recent pandemic have forced researchers across the globe to find out

alternative materials and methodologies for providing solutions the global issues. Continued growth of worldwide population in conjunction with highly volatile economics has placed increasing demands for energy and environmental protection at the forefront globally. Modernization of technologies and ever-increasing use of digitization even in the underdeveloped and developing nations like India urge researchers to engineer the materials at molecular level for desired applications, especially in the field of energy conversion and storage processes. Huge expenses associated with the modern-day requirements demand researchers to find out alternative, affordable yet beneficial materials and methods to solve some of the issues associated with energy and environmental sectors. A successful combination of electrochemistry along with materials chemistry can provide wonderful processes that can be used to solve energy crisis and environmental protection. In general electrochemistry in conjunction with materials chemistry offers a simple, cheap, ease to fabricate devices and provide alternative methodology to engineer the system at either atomic or molecular level to impart desired applications. In this context, this lecture will highlight the significance of multidisciplinary approach primarily using electrochemistry and allied fields. Particularly the experiments performed in our laboratory (Scheme 1) to tune and enhance the electron transport across the interface using various chemical modification processes will be highlighted. Importantly an example each for Fuel cells and microbial fuel cells [MFC] applications will be discussed. Electrocatalysts developed for direct alcohol oxidation and direct carbohydrate oxidation will also be presented. Recently a bi-functional catalyst based on hierarchically ordered nanoporous TiO_2 electrodes is developed for water

splitting reaction thereby simultaneous oxygen and hydrogen evolution reactions is proposed. Moreover, immobilization of microbes on the high surface area electrodes leads to specific catalytic activity of the prosthetic groups of enzymes present within the microbes which in turn demonstrated to be the potential anodes for microbial fuel cells applications. Moreover, some of the recent developments made at our laboratory in flexible electrodes as bioenergy conversion platforms will also be discussed. Further energy generated from biochemical reactions and from human excretory fluids will also be highlighted. In all these applications, electrochemistry is demonstrated to be a simple yet powerful technique to generate and convert renewable energy using modified interfaces.

Scheme 1: Pictorial representation of the fabrication of new and smart electrochemical materials for energy conversion and storage related applications.

Plenary Lecture 5

Novel hybrid halide perovskites based solar cells: The rise of perovskite photovoltaics

Prof. Manish K. Kashyap

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Hybrid halide perovskite (HHP) materials have gained unprecedented attentions among the photovoltaic community and are considered as promising candidates for the next generation solar cell technology. The HHP based solar cells have revolutionized the photovoltaic landscape with a rapid breakthrough in power conversion efficiency (PCE) of 26.4 % at present in just over a decade. Despite their enormous potential, these solar cells are still knocking the door of photovoltaic market due to instability problems associated with different materials employed during fabrication. In this talk, the roadmap of HHP based solar cells for transforming the photovoltaic scenario will be discussed in detail. Moreover, the perovskite material simulations and the device fabrication of novel HHP based solar cells will be taken into consideration to cover both experimental and theoretical aspects of research.

Keywords: Perovskite, efficiency, photovoltaics

Plenary Lecture 6

Terahertz Computed Tomography and its Prospectus

Dr. Mukesh Jewariya

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A novel technique has been demonstrated for the generation of intense terahertz electromagnetic wave that enables high-field near-single-cycle terahertz (THz) pulse via non-collinear $\chi^{(2)}$ process in LiNbO₃ with both phase-front and spectral angular dispersion. Using this technique, we can generate a single cycle (broadband) terahertz pulse up to an electric field of 750kV/cm

We have also demonstrated the potential of this intense THz pulse for 3D THz imaging, which is 13- times higher than that of previous system based on collinear optical rectification in ZnTe crystal. The main advantage of the proposed method relies on real-time THz line projection providing 10 ms acquisition time of 2D-ST THz image. Therefore, 3D THz CT has been performed in only 6 minutes, representing a significant improvement compared with common systems. Finally, demonstration of 3D images clearly indicated a high potential for sensing, non-destructive inspection and material characterization in real world applications.

Keywords: Terahertz, optical, tomography, 3D.

INVITED TALKS

Invited Talk 1

Smart Nanomaterials for Combating Antimicrobial Resistance

Dr. Vinay Kumar

Department of Biotechnology, Modern
College of Arts, Science and Commerce
(Savitribai Phule Pune University),
Ganeshkhind, Pune 411016, India

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Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR) is a condition when microbes including bacteria, viruses, fungi, and parasites evolve over time and no longer respond to medicines making infections harder to treat and increasing the risk of disease spread, severe illness, and death. Amongst these, the most pressing issue is bacterial resistance against commonly used antibiotics (referred to as Antibiotic Resistance, the ABR). The AMR has emerged as one of the most serious global public health threats in this century. Initially, this situation was considered a nosocomial issue and was confined mainly to the hospital environment but has now reached the community microbes thus posing a bigger challenge. Unfortunately, we are on the verge of the 'post-antibiotic' era, with only a handful of potent and novel antibiotics in recent decades, and the pipeline of effective antibiotics is drying. In a quest for effective and long-term solutions to this menace, several new approaches are being worked out to find effective, alternative antimicrobials. Nano-strategies employing smart, safe, and potent nanomaterials to

combat AMR and drug-resistant pathogens have been advocated in the context. This talk mainly focuses on current understandings and updates on AMR, especially in WHO-identified critical priority pathogens, their occurrence and spread, and major drug-resistance determinants acquired by these pathogens. Special emphasis is on our group's work on Mula-Mutha river ecosystems in the Pune region, the extent and magnitude of ABR in isolated bacterial strains from therein, co-tolerance with other environmental toxicants and targeting them with smart phytochemicals and nanomaterials. Successful attempts for optimal synthesis, functionalization, and characterization of nanomaterials and assessing their potencies against different ABR bacterial strains and underlying mechanisms of action, besides their cytotoxicity analyses, are covered in the talk.

Keywords: AMR, ABR, MDR, XDR, critical priority pathogens, smart nanomaterials, community microbes.

Invited Talk 2

Emerging Trends in Next Generation Solar Photovoltaic Technology for a Sustainable Future

Dr. Basudev Pradhan

Department of Energy Engineering, Centre of Excellence (CoE) in Green and Efficient Energy Technology (GEET), Central University of Jharkhand, Ranchi, India

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These days, the global energy crisis is emerging as one of the most significant issues facing humanity. In every year, the global electricity consumption also increases continuously, particularly in developing nations like our own where there is a severe lack of electricity. However, fossil fuels are limited, thought to run out and also are held responsible for increased concentration of carbon dioxide in the earth's atmosphere, which causes global warming. The consequences of the effect are already seen as an increase in the frequency and severity of natural disasters. These drew the attention to urgently develop environmentally friendly renewable energy sources. One of the renewable energy sources is photovoltaic (PV) technology, which generates electricity directly from solar radiation. The photovoltaic cells have become extensively studied since the 1950s when the first crystalline silicon solar cell, which had an efficiency of 6%, was developed at Bell Laboratories. Since then, the efficiency has reached 26.3% for crystalline Si solar cells, which is already close to the theoretical predicted upper limit of 31%. Today's photovoltaic modules are extremely safe and reliable products, with minimal failure rates and projected service lifetimes of 20 to 30 years. Due to the high cost of crystalline silicon solar cells, different emerging new-generation solar cells based on different materials like organic, organic-inorganic hybrid perovskite, and different Quantum dot materials, are down the line to take over the PV market. Recently, the solution-processed organic tandem photovoltaic cell has achieved a record 17.3 % efficiency. The perovskite solar cells are also one of the most promising PV technologies, which has achieved 26.7 % efficiency in single cell structure in just over

15 years of R & D research all over the world. If the stability issues of perovskite solar cells are solved then it will be the first next generation solar PV technology, which will be commercialized very soon with very low production cost, clean, green, and sustainable energy solution for the future.

Keywords: Energy, photovoltaics, silicon, perovskite, efficiency.

Invited Talk 3

Green and Renewable Hydrogen Fuel Production based on Metal Free Porous Carbon Materials

Siddhartha Samanta, Sahina Khatun and Dr. Anirban Pradhan

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Due to the rise of global warming and climate change, people have started moving away from fossil fuels and leaning towards green, renewable solar and wind energy. Hydrogen, as a renewable and clean energy resource, is a promising future fuel. Hydrogen production through metal-free electrocatalyst water splitting is crucial for obtaining sustainable and clean fuel. Plentiful, economically viable, and easily processed materials are commercially important for green hydrogen production. 1-5 Herein, we are devoted to developing greener energy through the integration of chemistry and materials, optimal utilisation of carbon resources, chemical energy storage and conversion, and commercially viable low-cost carbon material preparation

for energy production and storage applications.

Sustainable Energy & Fuels, **2024**, 8,4183-4191.

Optoelectronic devices such as OLED, Photovoltaic devices, Nano-Graphene, Transistors, storage devices (battery), capacitors are advantageous for countries such as India whose infrastructure is in demand for easy to implement technology.

References

- [1] *Electrochemical Stimuli-Driven Facile Metal-Free Hydrogen Evolution from Pyrene-Porphyrin-Based Crystalline Covalent Organic Framework*. S. Bhunia, S. K. Das, R. Jana, S. C. Peter, S. Bhattacharya, M. Addicoat, A. Bhaumik, **A. Pradhan***, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2017**, 9, 23843.
- [2] *A Metal-Free Covalent Organic Polymer for Electrocatalytic Hydrogen Evolution*. B. C. Patra, S. Khilari, R. N. Manna, S. Mondal, D. Pradhan, **A. Pradhan***, A. Bhaumik, *ACS Catal.* **2017**, 7, 6120.
- [3] *Surface Modified Porous Organic Polymer for Metal-Free Electrocatalytic Hydrogen Evolution Reaction*, **A. Pradhan***, R. Manna, *ACS Applied Polymer Materials*. **2021**, 3, 1376.
- [4] *Photoelectrochemical water splitting by triazine based covalent organic framework*. **A. Pradhan***, M. A. Addicoat, *Sustainable Energy & Fuels*, **2022**, 6, 4248-4255.
- [5] *A metal-free perylene-porphyrin based covalent organic framework for electrocatalytic hydrogen evolution*. S. Samanta, S. Khatun, I. Mukherjee, S. Maity, M. A. Addicoat, and **A. Pradhan, ***

Invited Talk 4

Functional Supramolecular Metallogel and Metalhydrogel

Dr. Biswajit Dey

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The concept of supramolecular chemistry adored in nature. The manifestation of science and technology covering physics, chemistry and biology demands the progress of supramolecular phenomena. Mimicking the nature chemists are exploring the supramolecular chemistry for offering laboratory-made artificial functional stuffs. In this context, the exploration of crystalline, liquid and solid type materials mainly earns critical attention in the research and development zones. But present demand highly triggers to explore semi-solid type mechanically flexible matters like gels. The idea of forming gels including organogel and hydrogel are well-documented. The environmental feasibility of hydrogel is commonly esteemed. Introduction of metal-resources into the gel-structure critically enhances the functional features of gel-like semi-solid object. Based on the nature of gel-immobilized solvent, metal-directed gels are classified as Metallogel with organic solvent-entrapment and Metalhydrogel having high content of trapped-water. Significances of Metallogel and Metalhydrogel are effective for numerous practical uses including

semiconducting application, self-healing material formation, biological applications, non-linear optical features, etc.

Invited Talk 5

Sustainable Materials for Bio-Engineered Graft Fabrication

Dr. Archna Dhasmana

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An increasing demand in the healthcare industry for innovative solutions, bio-engineered grafts are becoming more popular due to their sustainability, efficiency, and environmental friendliness. A key component of graft fabrication for biomedical applications is the incorporation of sustainable materials derived from renewable resources for scaffold fabrication mimic to the native tissue. Researchers are working on tackling challenges related to biocompatibility, mechanical strength, and environmental sustainability by incorporating biomaterials derived from renewable resources, such as plant-based polymers, marine biopolymers, and biodegradable composites. Our focus should not only be on availability, but also on the design and fabrication process of bioengineered grafts, highlighting advances in nanotechnology, 3D printing, tissue engineering, and the selection of R materials, i.e. renewables, reusables, regenerates, reconditions, repairs, and remodelling. Hence, we should emphasize functionalization of sustainable materials to promote cellular integration, tissue

regeneration, and reduce environmental impact. Several case studies and applications also demonstrate the potential of these materials in clinical settings, such as wound healing, vascular grafts, and organ repair. Consequently, by exploring the challenges and potential of using sustainable materials in healthcare, we aim to inspire researchers and students to innovate at the intersection of sustainability and biomedical engineering, paving the way for eco-conscious advances in regenerative medicine.

Keywords: Biomedical, polymers, 3D printing, healthcare, nanotechnology.

Invited Talk 6

Artificial Intelligence in veterinary and other Agri-allied sciences - scope, constraints and future prospect

Dr. Nandani Kumari^{1*}, Dr. Shailendra Kumar Rajak² & Dr. Pallabi Ghosh³

Assistant Professor cum Junior Scientist, Dept. of AGB, CoVS & AH., BAU, Ranchi

¹ Presenting author and main author, ² Assistant Professor Cum Junior Scientist (AH), Department of LPM, Co. V. S. and AH, BAU; ³ PG Scholar, Dept. of Vety Surgery and Radiology, Co. V. S and AH, BAU

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INTRODUCTION-Artificial intelligence is a set of modern tools and technologies by which computers replace human for works or tasks performed hitherto typically by human like observing, understanding, analyzing data, translating, recommending,

suggesting, decision making etc. Visual perception, speech recognition, decision making were hitherto beyond the ambit and scope of computer. With the advent of advanced technology appropriately labelled as artificial intelligence, this boundary is also literally vanishing making computers approximately approaching the Human in intelligence in a very subtle and clear ways which could be as beneficial as a great revolution or as catastrophic as a volcanic eruption if not handled or used ethically.

Applications of Artificial Intelligence in Veterinary Sciences

Although the applications of artificial intelligence are innumerable and ever increasing, the following important applications of artificial intelligence showcases the growing realms and scope of A.I. Automatic milking, estrous Detection, robotic Vaccination, as food supply chain monitor, Zoonotic Disease monitoring, Disease Diagnosis, Epidemiology and surveillance, Development of Disease Model, Patient assessment treatment and evaluation, Soft tissue and invasive surgery, are just few out of the innumerable fields of application of artificial intelligence in veterinary sciences.

Application of Artificial intelligence in Agricultural sciences

Drones are getting popular day by day and are being used for diverse applications in Agricultural sciences. They are the best example of strengthening scope and ambit of AI in Agri-allied fields. With the migrating labours and scarce labour available for agriculture in rural areas, this could be a boon for financially strong farmers. Weather forecasting, assessing the health of soil and plant, monitoring the pH of soil, precise assessment of pesticide dose thus reducing the pesticides required, crop monitoring,

harvest and yield assessment and surveillance are few of the important applications of Artificial intelligence in Veterinary sciences.

Limitations/Constraints of Artificial intelligence

The replacement of human with computer via Artificial intelligence might revolutionize the Agri-allied world but is bound to create unemployment. The ethical issues can't be ignored, and the result can be far too catastrophic to handle if not used judiciously. Stringent rules and regulations need to be made along with increasing usage of AI. In a developing nation like India, handling of AI based tools, and computer shall require proper training to ensure accuracy of result. For this training and courses for both the scientists and personnels should be devised and conducted first before completely inundating the field with AI tools.

Conclusion- Despite the current limitations and disadvantages, the fact that foray and elaborate use of Artificial Intelligence has been welcomed by the majority and is bound to increase and find a strong place in the Agri-and allied sciences. Future roadmap for effective, ethical and humanitarian use of AI is essential. Steps could be taken to generate employment based on AI to curb the unemployment menace created out of AI.

Keywords- Drones, Artificial intelligence, radio imaging, Robotic vaccination

Invited Talk 7

Advanced physics informed neural network algorithms for strongly coupled systems having boundary layers

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Development of deep learning algorithms is one of the challenging direction to solve engineering models. In this talk, I shall focus on the computational difficulties to solve the coupled system of differential engineering models where the convection matrix is not diagonally dominant. It is observed that one cannot get convergent approximations through upwind schemes. However, a boundary layer adaptive solution can be obtained through advanced deep learning-based iterative algorithms for these reaction-convection-diffusion systems. My aim through deep learning algorithms, is to relax this specific choice for the convection matrix. Recently, deep learning algorithms have gained significant interest for efficiently solving boundary value problems without using the a priori structure of the solution. However, due to spectral bias, they also encounter difficulties in approximating these coupled systems. To address these issues, I describe an iterative unsupervised deep learning algorithm to capture the layer behavior of singularly perturbed systems. Additionally, the presented algorithm will improve the neural network output without using the interpolation of the error monitor function.

Keywords: Deep learning, algorithms, models, unsupervised, interpolation

Invited Talk 8

Warm rolling-based microstructural engineering to overcome the strength-ductility trade-off in a medium manganese steel

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Advanced high-strength steels (AHSS) are the forefront structural material for applications requiring the combination of strength and ductility. Medium manganese steels are one of the emerging 3rd generation AHSS which can be processed suitably to impart such properties. However, any metallurgical approach to enhance strength is associated with a loss in ductility and vice-versa, a phenomenon commonly referred to as strength-ductility trade-off. Microstructural modification via thermomechanical processing optimization is one of the promising metallurgical solutions to this enduring problem of strength-ductility trade-off. In the present work, we modified the microstructure of a medium manganese steel via a novel low-temperature warm rolling (WR) treatment to overcome the strength-ductility trade-off. Controlled generation of dislocations in the constituent austenite and ferrite phases along with the introduction of twins in the

austenite phase, both induced by WR fetched an improvement in the yield strength compared to the steel conventionally treated by intercritical annealing. Additionally, austenite stability regulation via deformation above the M_d temperature during WR led to simultaneous improvement in ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and ductility as compared to the steel treated with IA. The achieved combination of yield strength and tensile toughness (product of UTS and total elongation) in the steel treated with this novel WR technique was significantly superior in comparison to the medium manganese steels with similar composition processed through different other innovative techniques reported to date. The present study demonstrates an approach to tailor the defect microstructure for escaping the near-ubiquitous strength-ductility paradox in metastable FCC alloys such as stainless steel, HEAs, TWIP steels etc.

Keywords: Strength-ductility trade-off, Austenite stability, Warm rolling, TRIP-TWIP, Medium manganese steel.

TRACK 1

Advanced Materials Science and Applications

ICEMIT MAT103

Equations of State Method for Contact Angle Interpretation

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Particular attention has been paid to the process of determining the tensions of solid surfaces based on the static contact angles that are already in existence. If the surface tension of a solid surface remains constant, contact angle patterns obtained from experiments are used to determine the surface tension between the solid and vapor phases. This is done using Antonow's equation of state [1] and Berhtloet's equation of state, employing three distinct methods. The first method involves the application of the combining rule [2], the second method involves a modified combining rule [3], and the third method involves the use of a different modifying factor [4] and the equation of state proposed by Neumann et al. [5]

Keywords: *Equations of state, Contact angles, liquid vapour interfacial tensions and Zisman plot*

ICEMIT MAT105

Study of Virial Coefficients of Polymer Solutions: Osmotic Pressure

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In this work, the experimental data of osmotic pressure for polystyrene sample in cyclohexane at three temperatures [1] and the experimental data of aqueous solution of Lysozyme in the salts (ammonium sulphate, ammonium oxalate and ammonium phosphate) at ionic strength 1 or 3M and with value of pH 7, pH 8 at 250 C [4-6] have been graphically analyzed to know the molecular parameters, molecular weights and virial coefficients. The molecular parameters for these solutes, calculated graphically by slope-intercept method for the osmotic pressure data, were found satisfactory. Thus, we find that at 200C the slope, that is, the virial coefficient B, is negative and for other two temperatures i.e., at 34.50C and 500C, it is

positive. The value of the intercept, that is the molecular weight M_n , found to be 2 g/mol approximately. The molecular weight is constant, but the virial-coefficient is not as it is temperature dependent. In order to establish the virial coefficients for a particular solute-solvent system, empirical methods are utilized. As opposed to the higher order virial coefficients, which are associated with a correspondingly larger number of solute particle clusters interacting with the solvent, the second virial coefficient is a representation of the interaction of a single solute particle with the solvent. Because of this, the second virial coefficient is a measurement of the interactions between particles, virial coefficients appear as coefficients in the virial expansion of the pressure of a many-particle system in powers of the density, providing systematic corrections to the ideal gas law. They are characteristic of the interaction potential between the particles and in general depend on the temperature. It is important to note that the third virial coefficient incorporates the contribution from three-body clusters, which means that it represents a significant number of interactions between solute particle clusters and the solvent. The virial expansion is characterized by the presence of larger and larger clusters of particles, which dictate the higher-order terms. The results of this study have demonstrated that the description of the second virial coefficient that is produced from a certain physicochemical process requires a higher level of caution than was previously studied.

Keywords: Osmotic Pressure, Virial Coefficients, Polymer Solution, Salt

■ ICEMIT MAT106

Impact of Vibration on Weld Quality, Properties and Microstructure in Vibration

Assisted Tungsten Inert Gas (TIG) Welding: A Review

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Vibration Assisted Tungsten Inert Gas (TIG) welding is an advanced approach that improves the efficiency of the conventional TIG welding process by incorporating mechanical vibrations while welding. Even though the benefits of vibration assistance have been shown in much research, a thorough understanding of the proper vibration parameters, such as frequency, amplitude, and modes for different materials, is still lacking. This review study offers a thorough examination of how vibrations affect the mechanical characteristics, residual stress, microstructure, and weld quality of the TIG welding process. It's been shown that incorporation of vibration can eliminate defects like porosity and cracking, enhance tensile strength, hardness, impact strength, and refine grain structure. This review article focuses on the ways that vibration affects heat distribution, solidification processes, and molten pool behavior.

Different parameters are explored concerning how they impact on the geometry of the weld bead and material properties, including vibration frequency, amplitude, and welding current. It highlights possible applications of vibration-assisted TIG welding in sectors like aerospace, automotive, and nuclear that demand high precision and durability. A thorough analysis of recent research and experimental results is presented. The review also describes the difficulties and constraints involved in placing vibration-assisted TIG welding into practice, providing information about potential future research options for improving the process for industrial applications

Keywords: Welding, vibration, mechanical, frequency, solidification

■ ICEMIT MAT107

A Review on Recent Advancement in Gas Tungsten Arc Welding (GTAW)

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Gas Tungsten Arc Welding (GTAW), commonly referred to as Tungsten Inert Gas (TIG) welding, has become a vital technique in many industries because of its accuracy, superior welds, improved microstructure, and finer grain hardness. It is widely utilized in the welding of nearly all ferrous and non-ferrous metals as well as thin materials. The TIG welding technology has undergone

numerous advancements in recent years that have greatly strengthened both the efficiency and quality of the weld. Technological advancement including hot-wire TIG welding, pulsed TIG, and vibration assisted TIG welding have reduced heat-affected zones, improved weld pool penetration and improved overall weld quality. Furthermore, precise control over the welding parameters has been made possible by the integration of automation, real-time monitoring, and artificial intelligence, resulting in more reliable and superior welds. The main objective of this review article is to explore the recent technological advancements which affect the performance, quality of the weld, and a range of applications of TIG welding in many different industries, such as the nuclear, automotive, and aerospace sectors. Therefore, a variety of TIG welding studies are gathered and examined in this review study, considering tests, parameters, and the types of materials utilized for welding.

Keywords: Gas Tungsten Arc Welding (GTAW), TIG, Activated GTAW, Flux Zone GTAW, Pulsed Current GTAW, Vibration Assisted GTAW

ICEMIT MAT112

Revolutionizing Medical Education and Research: The Role of Virtual Dissection Tables in Biomaterial Evaluation

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A Virtual Dissection Table (VDT) (Figure 1) is an innovative device that offers a detailed, interactive, and three-dimensional representation of the human body. As the demand for innovative methods in advanced biomaterial testing grows, VDT provides a cutting-edge approach for simulating the integration of biomaterials within the human body. Researchers and medical students can observe high-resolution 3D imaging of human anatomy and study in real-time the detailed interaction of biomaterials—such as implants, prosthetics, and tissue scaffolds with anatomical structures in, three-dimensions. This would enable researchers to assess factors such as structural integrity, biocompatibility, and the potential for wear and tear under various physiological conditions.

Figure 1: The first Virtual Dissection Table to be made in India

With VDTs, users can explore the effectiveness, compatibility, and safety of biomaterials in the context of male, female, pediatric male, pediatric female, and geriatric bodies. In conclusion, a VDT is an invaluable asset for attaining a deeper understanding of how biomaterials function within the human body for evaluating and optimizing the use of biomaterials in healthcare.

Keywords: Thermal Buoyancy, Richardson Number, Vortex Shedding, Darcy number, porous cylinder

ICEMIT MAT115

Thermal Buoyancy-Driven Vortex Shedding Behind a Porous Circular Cylinder at Low Reynolds Numbers

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In this investigation, we explore the impact of thermal buoyancy on vortex shedding behind a circular permeable cylinder. The study considers a range of parameters, including Reynolds number in the range of 10 to 40, Richardson Number spanning 0 to 2, and Darcy number from 10⁻⁶ to 10⁻². To analyze the flow and thermal field, we employ a control volume technique to solve the Darcy-Forchheimer-Brinkmann extended Navier-Stokes equation. The effect of thermal buoyancy and porosity on flow and thermal field is analysed by streamlines, vorticity and isotherm plots. Our findings reveal that within the specified Reynolds number range, the flow remains steady and

separated. However, the introduction of thermal buoyancy in a crosswise manner transforms the flow into unsteady periodic behaviour. We evaluate the critical Richardson number (Ri_{cr}) at which vortex shedding initiates for the given Reynolds number and Darcy number. Streamline, vorticity and isotherm plots, along with temporal variation v-velocity signal, vividly illustrate the resulting changes in flow structure. The result shows that for the increase in Darcy number at constant Reynolds number, the Ri_{cr} decreases, however when Reynolds number decreased at constant Darcy number, the Ri_{cr} increases.

Keywords: Thermal Buoyancy, Richardson Number, Vortex Shedding, Darcy number, porous cylinder

■ ICEMIT MAT118

Development of Eco-Friendly Corrosion and Wear-Resistant Ni-Graphene Nano-Composite Coating via Electroless Deposition Technique for Mild Steel Substrate

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This study presents the novel development of ecofriendly corrosion and wear-resistant hydrophobic Ni-graphene (Ni-G) nano-composite coating using electroless deposition technique on the mild steel substrate. Comprehensive characterization of the composite coating was conducted using various techniques including Raman spectroscopy, XRD, FESEM, EPMA, electrochemical corrosion tests, micro scratch tests, and contact angle measurements. FESEM analysis revealed a reduction in grain size upon graphene incorporation into the Ni matrix, indicating improved microstructure. EPMA analysis provided insights into the compositional distribution of the developed Ni-G composite coating. Electrochemical corrosion behavior was evaluated through potentiodynamic polarization and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy measurements in a 3.5 wt. % NaCl electrolyte, demonstrating significantly enhanced corrosion resistance with a corrosion inhibition efficiency of 94.8% for the Ni-graphene composite coating. Micro scratch testing revealed a notable increase in crack propagation resistance of the Ni-G composite coating compared to Ni-coating, approximately doubling its effectiveness. The results suggest that the developed Ni-G composite coating offers promising prospects for practical applications as a robust anti-corrosion coating, facilitated by the eco-friendly ELD technique.

Keywords: Graphene; Nanocomposite; Coating; Corrosion.

Keywords: Lead titanate, high energy ball milling, dielectric constant, Curie Temperature and dielectric loss etc.

■ ICEMIT MAT125

Impact on Dielectric Properties of Gd²⁺ Modified Lead Titanate Nanoceramics Prepared by High Energy Ball Milling Method

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Our expectation is that these modifications will be more dependent on the ionic radii difference. Such type of studies has hardly been reported as such lead titanate having perovskite structure has been selected as host lattice gadolinium has been selected as the source of guest ions. Ceramic powder has been fabricated by using High Energy Ball Milling (HEBM) method. Keeping these things in mind experimentations have been done in a systematic way. Dielectric constant is minimum for undoped lead titanate sample and increases by about five percent (5%) for gadolinium doped samples. It also appears from the figures that for five percent (5%) gadolinium samples T_c shift to higher temperature side.

■ ICEMIT MAT127

Metal-Oxide Modified Electrode for Floral Identification of Honey Using Electronic Tongue

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This work investigates a metal oxide-modified carbon paste electrode as a voltammetric sensor in an electronic tongue. A novel application of nanotechnology in the fabrication of tin oxide nanoparticles (SnO/Nps) serves as a modifier in carbon paste electrode for the floral classification of honey. The cyclic voltammetry technique is applied to study the electrode's behavior. The transient responses of the developed electrode for 40 samples of four different floral origins of honey have been treated with principal component analysis (PCA). Fig. 1 (a-b) shows the steps of SnO/Nps synthesis and cyclic voltammogram of SnO/Nps modified carbon paste electrode for four different floral type of honey respectively. The PCA score plot in Fig.1(c) shows the PC1 and PC2 total accumulative variances for the forty samples of SnO/Nps electrode. The score plot explains 93.67% of the variations in the data set for SnO/Nps electrode.

Thus, the score plot explains the discrimination capability of the tin oxide

nanoparticle-based carbon paste electrode. The class separability is measured to investigate the efficacy of the developed electrode. The result of the class separability index for PCA is 8.09. The new fabricated modified carbon paste electrode shows the utility of metal oxide modifier as a voltametric sensor for identification of floral variety of honey samples.

Figures 1. (a-c)

Fig. 1(a)

Fig.1(b)

Fig. 1(c)

Fig.1(a). Steps of SnO/Nps synthesis.

Fig.1(b). SnO/Nps modified carbon paste electrode for four different floral type of htypes.

Fig.1(c.) PCA plots of honey samples using SnO/Nps modified carbon paste electrode.

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■ ICEMIT MAT130

Ion Beam Deposition of Ag Nanoclusters on MoTe₂: A Computational Study of NO₂ Sensing

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This study investigates the enhancement of NO₂ gas sensing capabilities through the deposition of Ag nanoparticles on MoTe₂ monolayers using Ag ion beam irradiation, resulting in Ag_x-MoTe₂ (x=1-3) composites. Ag₃-MoTe₂ exhibits superior adsorption, electron transfer, and sensitivity, showing excellent reversibility and selective NO₂ detection. Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations reveal that NO₂ chemisorption is strongest on Ag₃-MoTe₂, with an adsorption energy of -1.694 eV, compared to -1.539 eV for Ag₂-MoTe₂ and -1.395 eV for Ag₁-MoTe₂. Furthermore, Ag₃-MoTe₂ shows the highest electron transfer to NO₂ (~0.417 e), significantly higher than Ag₂-MoTe₂ (~0.376 e) and Ag₁-MoTe₂ (~0.358 e). This indicates that Ag_x-MoTe₂ systems provide favourable adsorption/desorption characteristics, enhancing sensor reversibility. The calculated NO₂ sensing response is highest for Ag₃-MoTe₂ (~99%), followed by Ag₂-MoTe₂ (~97%) and Ag₁-

MoTe₂ (~93%). This enhanced sensitivity is attributed to the increased surface area and numerous adsorption sites provided by the Ag ion beam irradiation method. These findings suggest that Ag_x-MoTe₂ monolayers hold significant promise for selective and sensitive NO₂ gas detection applications.

Keywords: Nanocluster, Adsorption, transition metal dichalcogenide, gas sensor, density functional theory

■ ICEMIT MAT131

Efficient Helmet Detection Based on YOLO-V7 for Real-Time Safety and Monitoring System

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Monitoring of helmets is a crucial part of human safety nowadays. Accidents are increasing and causing deaths due to not wearing helmets. This paper proposes an intelligent system to detect whether a human or rider is wearing a helmet or not with details of the motorbike such as the number plate. The architecture combines You-Only-Look-Once version seven (YOLO-V7) to detect objects or helmets. The yolo-v7 architecture consists of a backbone, a

feature pyramid network (FPN), three detection heads (Headx3), and a path aggregation network (PAN). This network architecture assures the detection with a precision accuracy of 80.10%. The performance shows that the model can accurately recognize the helmets, motorbikes, and number plates that effectively detect utilizing the detection algorithm

Keywords: *Helmet monitoring, safety, YOLO-V7, artificial intelligence, intelligence system*

■ ICEMIT MAT132

Synthesis and Characterization of Hexagonal Boron Nitride for Gas Sensing Applications

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Hexagonal boron nitride (h-BN) is a notable inorganic compound that has gained significant attention due to its unique combination of electrical insulation, high thermal conductivity, lightweight structure, and chemical stability. Over the past decades, various h-BN nanostructures have emerged, retaining the material's intrinsic advantages while imparting unique

nanoscale properties. In this study, h-BN was synthesized using a boron oxide-assisted chemical vapor deposition (BOCVD) method, which facilitates in situ boron oxide vapor generation and promotes h-BN growth through its reaction with a nitrogen source. This method is now considered a benchmark in h-BN synthesis, offering high yield, purity, and scalability—qualities that make it highly suitable for industrial applications. Further analysis, including XRD for phase and grain size determination, as well as SEM and TEM for microstructural characterization, was performed on the synthesized h-BN, aiming to explore its potential for gas-sensing applications.

Keywords: *Hexagonal boron nitride (h-BN), Microstructure; TEM; Gas Sensing*

■ ICEMIT MAT134

Genotoxic and Cytotoxic effect of Bleaching powder on living cell

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Bleaching powder, a chemical substance commonly used in industrial and household applications, has prompted concerns about its possible cytotoxic and genotoxic effects on the living organism. This thorough article providing the existing corpus of data of the influence of bleaching powder exposure on cellular health. The paper begins by outlining the chemical composition of bleaching powder and its numerous applications, emphasizing the vast exposure potential to biotic and abiotic components of surrounding. The cytotoxic effects of bleaching powder on numerous cell types, spanning from human to microbial cells, are comprehensively investigated. Furthermore, this study examines the diversity in cell responses to bleaching powder exposure, considering aspects such as concentration, period of exposure. The assessment also covers the potential risks to health associated with chronic bleaching powder exposure, as well as its application in occupational contexts, environmental pollution, and issues related to public health. This paper provides a thorough examination of the cytotoxic and genotoxic effect of bleaching powder on somatic root tip cell of *Allium cepa*. The mitotic index percent and various chromosomal abnormalities like bridge, laggard, micronuclei, karyorhexis etc were observed. It emphasizes the importance of extensive research to better comprehend the long-term effects of exposure and to identify techniques for limiting possible damage while maintaining its critical applications.

■ ICEMIT MAT135

The future of nutraceuticals in Diabetes Management

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Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a common metabolic condition that can lead to many complications, including diabetic nephropathy (DN). Routine medical therapies for diabetes mellitus are ineffective and have numerous negative side effects. Furthermore, the global growth in the prevalence of diabetes leads researchers to investigate potential complementary or alternative treatments. Diabetes mellitus, one of the most dangerous noncommunicable illnesses, has long-term negative consequences for the healthcare system due to its microvascular and macrovascular symptoms, which can be fatal if not treated. Nutraceuticals, which combine natural materials with pharmaceutical agents, have a wide range

of therapeutic characteristics for a variety of pathological disorders, including DN. However, the specific underlying mechanisms are not entirely understood. Nutraceuticals, on the other hand, are alternative therapeutic options for orally eaten natural food elements that can be used to treat a variety of ailments, including diabetes. Nutraceuticals have been clinically proven to be useful in avoiding a variety of illnesses, including cancer, diabetes, heart disease, and kidney difficulties, due to their antioxidant properties and bioactive components. Several of these nutraceuticals contain flavonoids, a type of phytochemical. Cocoa, one of the flavanols used in diabetes treatment, offers an additional non-pharmaceutical intervention in diabetes management, thanks in part to its strong antioxidant capacity. Furthermore, flavonoids improve insulin resistance and sensitivity, dyslipidaemia, endothelial function, and blood pressure while decreasing oxidative stress and inflammation. As a result, they may be able to halt the advancement of diabetes's long-term vascular complications, including cardiovascular disease, neuropathy, nephropathy, and retinopathy. This review will focus on the effects of nutraceuticals (as an alternative treatment) on diabetic-related micro- and macrovascular issues.

■ ICEMIT MAT136

A perspective review on Interlinkage between Polycystic Ovary Syndrome and Diabetes Mellitus

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In this review, we systematically examine the intricate interplay between polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) and diabetes mellitus, focusing on the pathophysiological mechanisms, epidemiological associations, and clinical implications of their coexistence. PCOS, a prevalent endocrine disorder in reproductive-aged women, is characterized by hyperandrogenism, oligo-anovulation, and polycystic ovaries. Diabetes mellitus, a metabolic disorder marked by hyperglycaemia, can manifest as either type 1 or type 2. The intricate relationship between these conditions is explored through hormonal, metabolic, and genetic perspectives, shedding light on the bidirectional influence they exert on each other. Epidemiological evidence illustrating the increased risk of diabetes in women with PCOS and vice versa is discussed, along with potential contributing factors such as insulin resistance, obesity, and

inflammatory pathways. Furthermore, the review addresses the clinical implications of this comorbidity, including challenges in diagnosis, therapeutic interventions, and long-term health outcomes. Insights into emerging research and potential future directions for investigating the underlying mechanisms and personalized management strategies are also discussed. This comprehensive review aims to enhance our understanding of the complex interconnections between PCOS and diabetes mellitus, providing a foundation for improved clinical management and targeted interventions for individuals affected by this dual-endocrine disorder.

■ ICEMIT MAT138

Study of axis symmetric shapes of sessile drops

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By fitting the Laplacian equation of capillarity to the dimensions of sessile drops, axis symmetric drop shape analysis (ADSA) techniques are presented for the computations of anyone (the contact angle, the interfacial tension, and the radius of curvature at the drop apex) if the values of two other are known. With the change of area of pendant drops, the change in Gibb's energy and the change in work done are computed. Numerically generated drop

profiles used to demonstrate the accuracy and applicability of the method.

Keywords: *Lead titanate, high energy ball milling, dielectric constant, Curie Temperature and dielectric loss etc.*

■ ICEMIT MAT139

Advances in the Synthesis and Bioactivity of Fused N & O-Heterocycles: Microwave-Assisted Multicomponent Reactions

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Fused N & O-Heterocycles are a structurally diverse class of heterocyclic compounds with remarkable pharmacological significance. Advancements in microwave-assisted multicomponent reactions (MCRs) have revolutionized their synthesis, offering catalyst-free, efficient, and environmentally benign pathways characterized by reduced reaction times and high yields. This study provides an integrated overview of recent progress in the synthesis of fused N & O-Heterocycles through MCRs, focusing on structurally versatile derivatives such as pyrroles, pyridines and pyrans fused with quinolones, naphthoquinones, coumarins, and pyrones. The biological potential of these compounds is explored, emphasizing their promising roles as anticancer, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial agents. Supporting evidence from in silico predictions and in vitro evaluations

highlights their relevance in modern drug discovery and therapeutic development. By consolidating synthesis methodologies, bioactivity profiles, and future research perspectives, this study underscores the pivotal role of fused N & O-Heterocycles in advancing medicinal chemistry and their potential to inspire innovative pharmaceutical applications.

Keywords: *N & O-Heterocycles, MCRs, microwave, pharmaceuticals, bioactivity*

■ ICEMIT MAT140

Various Revolutionized Nanoparticles Targeting the Bcr-Abl Genes in Chronic Myeloid Leukemia Patients

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Chronic myeloid leukemia (CML) is a disorder basically concerning the dysfunctioning of the hematopoietic stem cells that leads to uncontrolled growth of white blood cells in the blood. Various novel diagnosis and treatment approaches have been achieved since past years. The most

common and very first employed compounds for treatment were tyrosine kinase inhibitors (TKI) that targeted the Abl and Bcr gene. Imatinib was the first tyrosine kinase inhibitor that was used in the first line treatment of CML in 2001. In passing years second line treatment was introduced by different second generation TKIs (2G-TKIs) such as Dasatinib, Bosutinib and Nilotinib were used when resistance and intolerance to Imatinib was found in the CML patients. These were more efficient and potent than Imatinib. Other than these TKIs, the transplantation of hematopoietic stem cells was also implemented in cases where the response of 2G-TKIs were inadequate and if still the point mutation T3151 was noticed. Depending upon the stages of CML and condition of the patient certain advances were also made in research for treatment of this disorder.

Keywords: *CML, Hematopoietic stem cells, Treatment, TKI, Imatinib, Resistance, 2G-TKIs, Allogenic Stem Cell Transplantation*

■ ICEMIT MAT141

Risk factors associated with the development of Diabetes in Women

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The term “risk factor” refers to a set of circumstances that raise the probability of a particular event or outcome, such as the onset of a disease, an impairment to one's health, or a poor outcome in a particular area of investigations. Diabetes mellitus (commonly known as Diabetes) is a disease in which the body's ability to create or respond to the hormone insulin is compromised, resulting in improper carbohydrate metabolism and increased blood glucose levels. Diabetes was the 9th greatest cause of mortality in 2019, with 1.5 million deaths directly related to the disease. Type 1 diabetes, Type 2 diabetes, and gestational diabetes are the three most frequent kinds of diabetes.

Type 1 diabetes typically occurs in children, while it can also affect adults. A few prevalent risk factors include past medical history, pancreatic illness, age and genetics. Insulin resistance is another name for Type 2 diabetes. The body produces insulin but is unable to use it, which is linked to risk factors such as family background, ethnicity, obesity, and certain health conditions. Family history and ethnic background are a couple of associated risk factors.

Diabetes in women is a rising concern, as it raises the possibility of heart diseases (the most frequent diabetic consequence) by 4 to 5 times in women. Other diabetic consequences, including blindness, kidney disease, and depression, are more common in women. Changes in lifestyle, such as a healthy diet and weight loss, can aid in its prevention or delay. Diabetes is however, a lifelong condition once diagnosed. Thus, the focus of this paper is on the various types,

risk factors, causes, and the related preventative actions of this disease in women.

Keywords: *Keywords: Diabetes (Type 1 and Type 2). Risk factors, Epidemiology, Result Analysis, Treatment and Prevention*

■ ICEMIT MAT142

Sickle Cell Anaemia: A Report on Neglected Chronic Disease of Increasing Global Health Importance

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Anaemia is a disease or condition where the concentration of red blood cells in the blood is below the normal range. It occurs when there is a lack of RBC count in the body which results into the reduced oxygen flow to all the organs of the body. Sickle Cell Disorders (SCD) are a group of blood disorders that are inherited from a person's parents. The most common type is known as Sickle cell anaemia. A genetic point mutation in the β -globin gene causes aberrant haemoglobin synthesis, which results in sickle cell anaemia (SCA). Prolonged deoxygenation causes the resultant haemoglobin tetramer to become weakly soluble, which leads to intracellular gelation of sickle haemoglobin and haemoglobin polymerization. Red cell membrane disruption from repeated sickling and unsickling cycles can result in haemolysis and vaso-occlusive events. The three main categories of sickle cell

anaemia's clinical manifestations include organ failure, including infection; pain and associated problems; and anaemia and its aftereffects. Millions of people worldwide suffer with sickle cell disease, which is more prevalent in areas with less medical facilities. Over 80 percent of sickle cell anaemia cases in India originate from the tribal districts across the country. The onset of sickle cell disease problems generally occurs between five and six months of age. Several health problems may develop, such as pain episodes (known as a Sickle Cell Crisis), anaemia, swelling in the hands and feet, bacterial infections, and stroke. The average life expectancy in the developed world is 40 to 60 years. Over the recent years, due to population migration, SCD now has a worldwide distribution and that a substantial number of children are born with the condition in higher-income area. Newborn screening, systematic clinical follow-up, prevention of sepsis and organ damage have led to an increased life expectancy among people with SCD in many such countries like India. However, due to lack of efficient programs for early detection and treatment, most affected children continue to die in early childhood. The majority of sickle cell anaemia treatment is still palliative in nature, encompassing supportive, symptomatic, and preventative methods.

Keywords: *Anaemia, Sickle Cell Anaemia, Survey Based Data Collection, Result Analysis*

■ ICEMIT MAT144

Design And Development of Robotic System for Welding Operation Using Soldering Gun on Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene (ABS) Material

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The last few decades have seen technological advancements in the field of modelling, simulation, manufacturing, assembly, and prototyping such as CNC (Computer Numerical Control) machining, milling, etc. Such technological advancements have now become widely adopted to meet the needs of today's economy. There is also a growing culture of hobbyists, makers, and tinkerers finding innovative ways to lower the costs of such technology. It has enabled the invention of low-cost manufacturing and assembly machines such as 3D printers, desktop PCB (Printed Circuit Boards) millers, fabricators, etc. The automated soldering of fabricated PCBs remains a costly ordeal where the market is dominated by expensive and sophisticated vision enabled soldering systems.

This paper focuses on designing, developing, and implementing a robotic

system tailored for welding operation using Solder gun. Each industry wants to maximize its productivity or minimize the cycle time of the manufacturing of the product. Welding/Melting of ABS (Acrylonitrile Butadiene Styrene) is a critical process in various industries, requiring precision and consistency, which can be effectively achieved through automation. Soldering with lead, or other metals used in soldering, can produce dust and fumes that are hazardous and can result in occupational asthma or worsen existing asthmatic conditions, as well as cause eye and upper respiratory tract irritation.

Keywords: *Robotic, Welding, Solder Gun, ABS, End Effector, ACO.*

■ ICEMIT MAT145

CFD-Based Study on the Thermal Performance of Encapsulated Phase Change Materials in Energy Storage

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Thermal Energy Storage Systems (TESS) offer a reliable and efficient solution for storing energy derived from renewable and waste sources. Energy plays a critical role across various sectors, including residential, industrial, transportation, communication, defense, and agriculture. This paper presents the development of mathematical models and numerical approaches for Latent Heat Thermal Energy Storage (LHTES) systems using phase change materials (PCM), specifically tailored for thermal energy management in electric vehicles. Numerical methods provide a powerful framework for analyzing the thermal behavior of LHTES systems. The study simulates the outward melting process of PCM encapsulated in a rectangular geometry within the LHTES system. The results highlight that the charging and discharging performance of the system is primarily influenced by the Stefan number (St), a dimensionless parameter governed by the interplay between latent and sensible heat properties.

Keywords: *Computational Analysis, Thermal Energy Storage System, Latent Heat, Thermal Energy Management, Electric Vehicle*

TRACK 2

Advanced Energy Technologies and Systems

ICEMIT EN101

Energy saving by using Heat Pump

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Heat Pump is a machine that transfers heat energy from a source to a sink. It uses the standard refrigeration air-conditioning cycle and exactly same components i.e. compressor, refrigerant gas, heat exchangers (evaporator/condenser). Instead of rejecting heat to the atmosphere, it uses a heat exchanger to transfer the heat from hot gas to water, thereby heating the water that can be utilized for various purposes like bathing, cooking, cleaning & washing and various medical, pharmaceutical and chemical processes.

Heat Pump uses a closed loop and works on a continuous repetitive cycle and thus results in an energy efficient process. Just for a broad comparison, a heat pump system produces 4 KW equivalent heat energy output with input of only 1 KW electrical energy vis a vis conventional electrical geysers/ heater produces 1 KW equivalent heat energy with 1 KW electrical power input. Thus, we can call it nearly 4 times as efficient compared to a conventional electric

geyser or in turn saves that much electrical power consumption.

Fig 1. Energy efficiency of a Heat Pump.

Fig 2. Working of a Heat Pump and the necessary conditions

■ ICEMIT EN103

Analyzing Range of an EV for Different Driving Cycles under Specific State of Charge Scenarios

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One of the primary challenges impeding the broader adoption of electric vehicles (EVs) is range anxiety—the concern that an EV may deplete its battery during a journey, particularly over long distances. Compounding this is the fear of power interruptions and the uncertainty regarding how far an EV can reliably travel before requiring a recharge. A vehicle's range is influenced by a variety of factors that affect energy consumption, including driving behavior, traffic conditions, ambient weather, terrain, and the weight of the vehicle's payload. This study proposes a model-based methodology for calculating the range of battery electric vehicles (BEVs), with a focus on real-world applicability. Data is obtained from multiple driving cycles (FTP 75, US06, SC03, UDDS and WLTP) under different conditions, allowing for an in-depth analysis of EV performance. The results offer critical insights into how various external factors impact vehicle range, especially under diverse environmental conditions. Furthermore, the analysis suggests that optimizing charging strategies can significantly enhance the operational endurance and practical

deployment of BEVs, ultimately contributing to their increased viability in everyday use.

■ ICEMIT EN106

Equation of state and excess energy for size asymmetric square well mixtures

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Results from the test of the new mixing rule³² were better than those proposed by Dieter's²⁹, Ely³⁰ and Jonha³¹. Perturbation theories are applicable to fluid mixtures to the same extent as that of the simple fluid. The one fluid model of van der Waals is verified within the framework of perturbation theory pertaining to fluid mixtures. In the present work, the computer simulations were used to predict the compressibility factors and excess energy for binary mixture for diameter ratio of 2/3.

■ ICEMIT EN109

Enhanced Bioethanol Production Using LCB

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Bioethanol production faces limitations such as low yield and high production costs, particularly with conventional feedstocks. This research work focuses on enhancing bioethanol production by utilizing cassava peels, a lignocellulosic waste material, as a second-generation feedstock. The shift from traditional feedstocks to renewable materials aims to increase production efficiency and reduce environmental impact. By applying pretreatment and fermentation techniques with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, we optimize the conversion of cassava peels into bioethanol. This approach addresses the challenges associated with existing bioethanol production methods while leveraging underutilized byproducts from the tapioca flour industry. We optimized the process using Response Surface Methodology (RSM) to analyze and fine-tune experimental conditions. Based on the data collected, we designed a reactor model for bioethanol production to further improve efficiency. The research work aims to advance renewable energy technologies, providing a promising solution to increase bioethanol yield, reduce production costs, and mitigate environmental impacts

Keywords: *Agro-industrial byproduct, Bioethanol yield optimization, Second-generation biofuel, Waste-to-energy, Bioethanol production, Renewable energy.*

■ ICEMIT EN110

Regulatory Framework and Consumer Protection: Policy Impacts on End Users in Solar Energy Storage Adoption

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The adoption of any new technology is faced with several challenges such as, barriers from existing well-established socio-technic setups and techno-economic uncertainties [1]. Hence, the proliferation of emerging technologies like solar energy storage (SES) devices requires support from policy makers to enable its development and acceptance at various stages of its emergence and diffusion. Policy makers behold the power to accelerate the transition to SES-assisted residential renewable energy scenario, via formulating complementary regulatory frameworks and policies [2]. The residential solar adoption in Australia is an example of a transition to renewable energy enabled via such policies [3]. In Australia, the high residential solar penetration is a consequence of the generous incentives and subsidies instilled by the government. A qualitative analysis involving 15 stakeholders from various categories indicated that the incentives and subsidies were instrumental in encouraging adoption among the end-users who would not have otherwise adopted the technology. The policies made the technology more accessible and popular among the consumers. Considering the case of Western Australia (WA), in particular, the adoption of residential solar is adding to the instability of the grid. Moreover, the adoption is moving towards a saturation while the incentives and subsidies are being recalled by the government. The consumers are now faced with a loss of excess power that could have been stored, and increased electricity costs. However, the pricing of the battery makes it inaccessible to majority of the consumers. There are also technology-

related uncertainties and the absence of regulatory frameworks enforcing installation standards for batteries. Here, the policy makers can play a significant role by redirecting the present incentives on residential solar towards SES devices. This will benefit the existing residential solar consumers, in the backdrop of disappearing incentives. Moreover, this will also encourage new adopters to make a transition to renewable energy on grounds of attaining energy security and reduced electricity costs. The study uses stakeholder theory to analyze the impact of policy interventions in moulding the consumer-attitude towards SES devices.

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ICEMIT EN113

Assessing the Cybersecurity Challenges in Virtual Power Plants Through Review of Risks and Resilience Strategies

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Virtual Power Plants (VPPs) are an essential element of the modern energy infrastructure, enabling efficient integration of distributed energy resources (DERs) and demand response systems. However, the reliance on digital communication technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), SCADA, and edge computing has introduced significant cybersecurity vulnerabilities into these systems. The decentralized and interconnected nature of VPPs broadens the attack surface, making them susceptible to a wide range of cyber threats, including Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS), ransomware, and data breaches. As cyber-attacks grow in sophistication and scale, securing VPPs becomes increasingly challenging.

This paper investigates the current cybersecurity landscape affecting VPPs, with a focus on identifying critical vulnerabilities and assessing the impact of various attack vectors. We review existing cybersecurity frameworks and models, such as deep learning-based threat detection and edge computing solutions, to enhance the resilience of VPP systems. The paper also explores the economic consequences of cyber-attacks on VPP infrastructure and presents a cybersecurity risk mitigation strategy that integrates real-time monitoring, machine learning algorithms, and advanced encryption technologies. By addressing these issues, this paper aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the challenges and possible solutions to securing virtual power plants in the evolving energy ecosystem.

Keywords: *Virtual Power Plants (VPPs), Cybersecurity, Edge-Based Security Architecture, Distributed Energy Resources, Smart Grid*

■ ICEMIT EN115

Improvement of Engine Performance Emission and Combustion Characteristics of Mahua biodiesel fuelled in constant speed CI Engine using FeCl₃ nanoparticle

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Global warming issues include harmful emissions, primarily NO_x, and the engine performance of renewable fuels like biodiesel and its blends. Due to the depletion of fossil fuels and rising energy prices, researchers have increasingly relied on substitute energy sources in the last ten years when adding nano-additives. In this study, biodiesel-diesel mixtures dispersed with ferric chloride (FeCl₃) nanoparticles as a fuel additive are tested on a 4-stroke single-cylinder VCR diesel engine at various loads (3, 6, 9, & 12 kgf) and a constant pressure of 180 bar for evaluating fuel performance, combustion, and emission

characteristics. In this work, the dosing quantity of FeCl₃ nanoparticles was varied from 50, 75, and 100 ppm into the Mahua oil biodiesel (B20) fuel blend with the assistance of an ultrasonicator. The engine tests revealed remarkable improvement with Nanofuel implementation, particularly under diverse load conditions. At a load of 12 kgf, the combustion parameters like NHRR, mean gas temperature, cylinder pressure, and BTE was increased by 18.46%, 5.74%, 12.29%, and 10.72%. The greatest decrement in BSFC was observed as 7.69% at B20+ 100 ppm FeCl₃. Compared to conventional diesel, there were significant reductions in the emissions parameters of CO, UHC, and smoke opacity with decreases of 42.68%, 9.73%, and 29.69% respectively. However, B20+ 100 ppm resulted in a 13.07% rise in nitrogen oxides (NOX). As a result, adding FeCl₃ nano additions enhanced overall engine performance and significantly reduced emissions from CI engines. So, in summary, we find that blending Mahua oil biodiesel (B20) with FeCl₃ nano additions significantly enhances engine performance and combustion while reducing emissions of pollutants.

Keywords: *VCR Diesel Engine, Engine Performance, Exhaust Emission, Mahua oil Ferric chloride, Nanoparticle size.*

■ ICEMIT EN116

Innovative Approaches to Electrifying Transportation Systems: Challenges and Opportunities

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As the world steers its way into new transportation systems that have electrification at its core, it is on its way to replacing vehicles based on fossil fuels, and it will replace all these things with cheaper and friendlier options. The current paper discusses the status of electric vehicles, charging infrastructure, and government policies as added players in this revolution. The innovation in technology is the improvement in battery technology, intelligent charging solutions, vehicles-to-grid (V2G) systems, and autonomous electric mobility. While the challenges are daunting, there is high cost, low emission of carbon, generation of independent energy, and growth to become catalytic to ensure economic growth. The paper will outline case studies and strategic recommendations about repositioning a wholesomely electrified transportation network toward a future which entails an industry-wide commitment to work jointly with governments and consumers.

Keywords: *Electric Vehicles (EVs), Sustainable Mobility, Battery Technology, Charging Infrastructure, Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G), Autonomous Electric Vehicles*

■ ICEMIT EN119

Enhancing Grid Stability: Fault Ride-Through Protection for Motor-Generator Pair Systems in Renewable Energy

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Renewable energy systems, particularly those integrating motor-generator pairs, play a pivotal role in the transition towards sustainable energy solutions. However, the reliability of these systems is often compromised by faults and disturbances in the electrical grid. This study presents a comprehensive analysis and implementation of fault ride-through (FRT) protection for motor-generator pair systems within renewable energy frameworks. The proposed protection scheme aims to enhance system stability and continuity of operation during grid faults, thereby minimizing downtime and potential damage to equipment. The methodology involves the development of advanced control algorithms that detect and respond to voltage sags, swells, and other transient disturbances. These algorithms are embedded within a real-time simulation environment to validate their effectiveness under various fault conditions. Key performance indicators, such as voltage stability, current harmonics, and system response time, are meticulously analysed to ensure robust protection. Experimental results demonstrate that the implemented FRT protection scheme significantly improves the resilience of motor-generator pair systems. The system maintains

operational integrity during fault conditions, with minimal disruption to the overall power generation process. Additionally, the adaptive nature of the control strategy allows for seamless integration with existing renewable energy infrastructures, making it a viable solution for enhancing grid reliability. This research contributes to the field of renewable energy by providing a scalable and efficient approach to fault management, promoting the widespread adoption of motor-generator pair systems in modern energy grids. Future work will focus on the integration of machine learning techniques to further optimize the protection mechanisms and adapt to evolving grid conditions.

Keywords: motor-generator, renewable energy systems, power systems, power grid, solar pv.

■ ICEMIT EN122

Assessment of Barriers and Challenges in Undertaking Green Entrepreneurship and Green Market

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“Waste is not waste until we waste it-William” bridges the gap between the environment and the entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship is the solution for many developmental perspectives like economic, social development etc. Green entrepreneurship adds another edge of sustainable development not only by shielding the environment, but fielding in economic growth and employment generation. An increasing number of companies within the startup ecosystem are focusing on addressing climate-related problems. But these green entrepreneurs and start-ups certainly undergo various other hurdles and barriers. This research study is an attempt to understand as whether it is entrepreneurship that attracts youth, or it is youth who embraces entrepreneurship. The aim of the study is to understand and explore about various challenges / barriers in green entrepreneurship in Jharkhand. Whether ‘green entrepreneurship has more challenges/barriers than normal entrepreneurship’ has been tested though hypothesis. The findings of the survey on various types of challenges and barriers give useful precautionary and insight not only to the youth who are willing to embrace green entrepreneurship, but also to the policy makers in Jharkhand to extend institutional support and mentorship to budding entrepreneurs and green entrepreneurs.

Keywords: Barriers/Challenges, Business, Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurial Mindset, Green Entrepreneurship, Green Energy, Green Market, Start-up.

■ ICEMIT EN123

Application of Rayleigh Distribution for Micro-Wind Turbine Prediction: A Case Study on Wind Energy Potential in Gorakhpur District at 10m height

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Researching renewable resources has become essential, given the sharp rise in energy consumption and the desire for sustainable solutions. This research employs the Rayleigh distribution to evaluate the wind energy potential at a height of 10 meters in the Gorakhpur area of Uttar Pradesh. The goal of the study is to determine the best micro-wind turbines (MWTs) within the area and forecast wind power density (WPD). To determine Rayleigh parameter - scale variable, monthly data on wind speed from 1980 to 2023 was

examined. The process involves choosing MWT models according to their requirements after calculating the function of probability density and wind power density. The results highlight the potential for localized wind energy solutions in the area, supporting sustainable development objectives. The study lays the groundwork for increasing the use of renewable energy in semi-urban regions.

Keywords: *Wind energy, Micro wind turbines, Rayleigh distribution, Wind speed, Wind power density, Wind power, Wind, Turbines*

■ ICEMIT EN124

Application of Weibull Distribution for Micro-Wind Turbine Prediction: A Case Study on Wind Energy Potential in Jaisalmer District at 10m height

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Given the dramatic increase in energy use and the need for sustainable solutions, research into renewable resources has become crucial. In this study, the wind energy potential at a height of 10 meters in the Jaisalmer region of Rajasthan is assessed using the Weibull distribution. The study's objectives are to anticipate wind power density (WPD) and identify the best micro-wind turbines (MWTs) in the region. Monthly wind speed data from 1980 to 2023 was analysed to calculate Weibull parameters, such as shape and scale variables. After determining the function of probability density and wind power density, the procedure entails selecting MWT models based on their needs. The findings complement the goals of sustainable development by highlighting the possibility of localized wind energy solutions in the region. The study establishes the foundation for semi-urban areas to employ more renewable energy.

Keywords: Wind energy, Micro wind turbines, Weibull distribution, Wind speed, Wind power density, Wind power, Wind, Turbines

ICEMIT EN125

The Design and Innovation and Technological Advances in Pumped Hydro Storage System

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The Pumped Hydro Storage System (PHSS) is a well-known technology that is commercially available for the utility-scale power storage and it used since as the 1890s and 1st found in Italy and Switzerland. In this paper it explores very recent design innovations and technological advances in pumped hydro storage systems (PHS), which play a crucial role in energy storage and grid stabilization in future. And to balance the supply and demand, effective energy storage systems are crucial as renewable energy sources like solar and wind power grow in popularity now a days. Advanced turbine technology, improved materials for less environmental effects and the selection techniques are just a few of the advancements in PHS designs that are examined in this paper. It also emphasizes the incorporation of digital technologies that maximize operational efficiency and cut costs, like automation and predictive analytics. This research also emphasizes how PHS systems might help ensure a sustainable energy future by tackling issues like scalability and environmental concerns. The results advance our knowledge of how enhanced viability of pumped hydro as a crucial element in the shift to renewable

energy systems may be achieved using the unique engineering and technology.

Keywords: *Renewable energy, Pumped Hydro Storage Systems (PHSS), Advanced turbine, Variable-speed pumps, Grid stabilization, Hybrid systems, Improved turbines and pumps, Intelligent control mechanisms, Enhanced recoverability and efficiency.*

■ ICEMIT EN126

Global Potential of renewable Energy Sources: A Literature Assessment

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An increase in world energy demand to at least 1000 EJ (EJ = 10¹⁸ J) is predicted by widely cited estimates to be reached by 2050, assuming continued economic growth on the path established during the last few decades. The depletion of reserves and the growth in greenhouse gas emissions will therefore each necessitate a new energy regime in which fossil fuels are no longer dominant in the fuel mix. The investment in nuclear power is not likely to increase from the existing miniscule shares. This means renewable energy should supply most energy into the future. This paper tries to answer what levels of energy RE could eventually provide and over what

time frame. Adding in the energy expenses of energy we find it highly unlikely that RE could provide anywhere near 1000 EJ by 2050. We also show the net technical potential for RE will decrease if climate change continues to happen. Ultimately, a conclusion is drawn that the transition to renewable energy globally will have to be bridged with substantial cuts in general consumption of energy for the sake of sustainability of the environment.

Keywords: *renewable energy sources, Energy potential, Global energy demand, technical potential, Economic potential, Sustainability.*

■ ICEMIT EN127

Comparative analysis of bioethanol production yield between pre-treated and untreated rice-straw

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An increase in world energy demand to at least 1000 EJ (EJ = 10^{18} J) is predicted by widely cited estimates to be reached by 2050, assuming continued economic growth on the path established during the last few decades. The depletion of reserves and the growth in greenhouse gas emissions will therefore each necessitate a new energy regime in which fossil fuels are no longer dominant in the fuel mix. The investment in nuclear power is not likely to increase from the existing miniscule shares. This means renewable energy should supply most energy into the future. This paper tries to answer what levels of energy RE could eventually provide and over what time frame. Adding in the energy expenses of energy we find it highly unlikely that RE could provide anywhere near 1000 EJ by 2050. We also show the net technical potential for RE will decrease if climate change continues to happen. Ultimately, a conclusion is drawn that the transition to renewable energy globally will have to be bridged with substantial cuts in general consumption of energy for the sake of sustainability of the environment.

Keywords: *renewable energy sources, Energy potential, Global energy demand, technical potential, Economic potential, Sustainability.*

TRACK 3

Emerging Trends in Information Technology and Its Application in Materials Science

ICEMIT IT101

Attack Detection in Camera and Lidar in Smart Cars Using Time Delay Differential Equations

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With the rapid integration of advanced technologies into modern vehicles, the cybersecurity of smart cars has become a pressing concern. In this context, the utilization of Time Delay Differential Equations (DDEs) emerges as a promising approach for detecting cyber-attacks targeting smart car systems. This paper investigates the application of Time Delay Differential Equations for cyber-attack detection in smart cars. By modelling the temporal dynamics of smart-car systems and explicitly accounting for communication delays within interconnected components, Time Delay Differential Equations offer a

robust framework for identifying anomalies indicative of cyber threats. The proposed methodology encompasses system modelling, anomaly detection, and response mechanisms, aimed at enhancing the cybersecurity resilience of smart car systems. Through the formulation of mathematical models using Time Delay Differential Equations and the development of algorithms for real-time anomaly detection, this research aims to contribute to the advancement of cybersecurity measures in the automotive industry. The findings presented in this paper provide valuable insights into the potential of Time Delay Differential Equations as a tool for safeguarding smart cars against cyber-attacks, paving the way for safer and more secure transportation systems in the era of connected and autonomous vehicles.

Smart cars are vulnerable to cyber-attacks that endanger the safety and security of their passengers because of their advanced technology and networked systems. This study addresses the use of Time Delay Differential Equations (DDEs) in smart cars for cyberattack detection. The Study of dynamic behavior over time is made possible by the integration of DDEs into the modelling of smart automobile systems, with a focus on potential cyber vulnerabilities and communication delays. The suggested approach strengthens smart automobiles' defences against cyber-attacks by integrating reaction mechanisms, anomaly detection, and system modelling.

In context of advancing cyber-security solutions for the automobile sector, the paper gives a thorough approach to cyber-attack detection and mitigation.

Keywords: *RT Duroid, Medium gain antenna, S11, VSWR, Radiation Pattern, Mobile Communication*

■ ICEMIT IT104

RT Duroid dielectric material-based design and simulation of medium gain patch antenna for Sub-urban areas wireless communication

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Fifth generation and beyond technology has widespread all around the world requiring high gain antenna for the effective communication system. But for sub-urban areas or countryside network, the medium gain antenna is more significant due to its broader radiation pattern. This

paper presents an RT Duroid dielectric material-based patch antenna having volumetric dimension 11 mm × 12.64 mm ×

0.05 mm for sub-urban areas wireless communication. The designed antenna has five square slots of dimension 0.25 mm × 0.25 mm, two rectangular slots

having dimensions 1 mm × 0.25 mm and four circular slots having radius 0.125 mm on the patch of the antenna. The antenna is designed and simulated at 30 GHz through electromagnetic solver high frequency structure simulator (HFSS). The designed antenna provides four band characteristics at 25 GHz, 31 GHz, 37 GHz & 43 GHz with a gain of 5.2 dB and wider bandwidth of 1.89 GHz, at a return loss of -15.53 dB. For all bands voltage standing wave ratio

(VSWR) lies between 1 and 2, indicating good impedance match between the antenna and the

feed line. Novelty of the present work is identified in terms of the quadband feature, size miniaturization, cost effectivity, good directivity, gain and bandwidth. The proposed antenna is

suitable for the fifth-generation mobile communication in sub-urban areas, satellite communication etc.

Keywords: *RT Duroid, Medium gain antenna, S11, VSWR, Radiation Pattern, Mobile Communication*

■ ICEMIT IT110

Anesthesia Dosage Prediction: A Deep Learning Approach for Enhanced Patient Care

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Anesthesia Dosage prediction requires careful consideration of a number of factors such as patients' demographics, surgical procedure details and medical history, making it challenging for anesthesiologists. In this research, we focus on the task of using machine learning to predict the decisions made by anesthesiologists during surgeries. Specifically, we approach this task by treating the patient's medical data and the dosage administered during surgery as a supervised regression problem. An examination was conducted to assess the predictive performance using six different machine learning models: Random Forest, XGBoost, and ANN (artificial neural network), based on 2346 instances collected from real surgical procedures. The findings indicated that when predicting the propofol dosage, the ANN model achieved prediction scores of 0.761 for the coefficient of determination (R² value) and 0.00406 for mean squared error. This highlights the potential of using machine learning to forecast the decisions made by anesthesiologists.

Keywords: Anesthesia, Machine learning Algorithms, ANN, Random Forest, XGBoost, Demographics, Coefficient of determination, MSE, Anesthesiologist's decisions, Propofol Dosage.

■ ICEMIT IT111

Smart Solutions: Leveraging AI and Machine Learning in Tourism and Financial Sectors

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This study examines how machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) are revolutionizing the tourism and financial services industries. The report illustrates how AI and ML improve operational efficiency, personalize customer experiences, and foster innovation in several industries by examining a variety of implementations of these technologies. Important developments are reviewed, highlighting the substantial advantages they offer to both organizations and customers. This includes AI-powered chatbots in the tourism industry and real-time fraud detection systems in the finance industry. The paper also addresses the potential of AI and ML in the future, including developments in AI-driven investment strategies, intelligent itinerary planning, and dynamic pricing. Ultimately, it emphasizes how important it is for companies to adopt these technologies in order to survive and grow in the rapidly changing digital landscape. The findings suggest that proactive AI and ML adaptation is essential

for long-term success and growth in the quickly evolving market environment.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), Fraud Detection, Personalized Financial Services, Predictive Analytics, Dynamic Pricing, Sustainable Tourism.*

■ ICEMIT IT112

Smart industries: Leveraging IoT and Edge computing for innovation in healthcare and tourism sectors

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This paper delves into the revolutionary influence of Internet of Things (IoT) and Edge Computing technologies on smart industries, particularly in the healthcare and tourism sectors. IoT facilitates device connectivity for instant data gathering and communication, while Edge Computing brings computing capabilities nearer to data origins to decrease latency and improve decision-making. Industries are seeing advancements like telemedicine, remote patient monitoring, smart medical devices, and improved hospital management in healthcare through the integration of these technologies. In the tourism industry, IoT and Edge Computing are also contributing to smart hotels, tailored guest experiences, and efficient resource management by processing local data. The article discusses the main uses, chances, and obstacles of

implementing IoT and Edge Computing in these industries. It focuses on the advantages of improved data protection, instant data analysis, and eco-friendly resource control, while also tackling issues such as scalability, compatibility, and expenses. Additionally, upcoming developments like the merging of AI, 5G, and automation are described as drivers for more innovation. By analysing real-life examples, the paper offers practical observations on how these technologies are changing various sectors, proving their importance in increasing effectiveness, improving customer interactions, and supporting environmental responsibility.

Keywords: *Internet of things, edge computing, telemedicine, healthcare, tourism sectors*

■ ICEMIT IT113

AI Based detection of phytochemicals regulating Cholesterol Level

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High cholesterol levels are a significant risk factor for cardiovascular diseases and managing them is crucial for maintaining

overall health. Our lifestyle management is contributing in the increased risk of cholesterol. Pharmaceutically various synthetic compounds are available to manage the cholesterol level, but they have certain side effects. Hence, naturally available phytochemicals have always been a choice to replace the synthetic compounds. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is proving valuable in screening for cholesterol-lowering phytochemicals, leveraging machine learning algorithms and big data to identify bioactive compounds that may reduce cholesterol levels. This study focuses on in silico screening of bioactive phytochemicals to identify potential candidates for modulating cholesterol metabolism in the liver. For this published literature, patents, and databases to identify promising hepatoregulatory phytochemicals were surveyed. Around 60 phytochemicals were selected and queried for Pa and Pi (Pharmaceutically active and Inactive) value in way2drug (<https://www.way2drug.com/passonline/>) online server for hepatoprotective property, cholesterol synthesis inhibitor, cholesterol absorption inhibitor and cholesterol antagonist. The phytochemical showing the best activity were analysed for ADME (Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, and Excretion) properties were analysed using SwissADME tool (<http://www.swissadme.ch/>). Structure-Activity Relationship (SAR) Modelling were done using HADDOCK docking server (<https://rascar.science.uu.nl/haddock2.4/>). The best fitted structure were simulated for 100ns to get insight of the stability and efficacy of phytochemicals in various environments, helping researchers to optimize them for better bioavailability and cholesterol-lowering action.

Keywords: *in silico screening, phytochemicals, hepatoprotectant, isomeric smiles, hypercholesterolemia.*

■ ICEMIT IT115

Transparency and Efficiency: Blockchain for Modern Supply Chain Management

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Blockchain technology has emerged as a revolutionary force in SCM with high transparency, efficiency, and security. In this paper, we are going to explore very basic features of blockchain, which include immutability, decentralization, and real-time traceability, and analyze their implications on SCM. We discuss the landscape of BC-SCM systems, analyzing the state-of-the-art systems from the view of critical security requirements and possible threats. It portrays some critical mistakes that are occurring nowadays in the systems and offers some better solutions which could ensure that no known as well as unknown attacks occur without compromise. This holistic approach towards this makes sure that transparency as well as proactive detection of threats build up trust and innovation within the supply chains. Such practical applications include Walmart and De Beers, and much more is in store through the implementation of blockchain

technology in fulfilling the requirements of a sustainable and resilient supply chain.

Keywords: *Blockchain, Supply Chain Management, Efficiency, Security, Immutability, Decentralization, Real-time Traceability, Smart Contracts.*

■ ICEMIT IT117

Deep Reinforcement Learning for Resource Optimization in UAV-Enabled Wireless Networks

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The paper offers a resource optimization that optimizes the user and power for a UAV-assisted wireless network to maximize the network's total throughput while satisfying the quality of service (QoS) requirements of the users. UAV-assisted wireless networks state to a communication infrastructure where unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) are used as flying base stations to provide wireless connectivity to ground users. UAV-assisted wireless networks have several advantages over traditional ground-based wireless networks,

such as increased coverage, better mobility, and reduced infrastructure costs. The users are positioned in a coverage area. The UAV can dynamically adjust its altitude and position to optimize the network performance. A deep reinforcement learning (DRL) can be used to solve the user association and resource allocation problem in UAV-assisted wireless networks. The problem can be formulated as a decision-making problem, where the UAV has to learn the optimal action to take at each time step to maximize a reward function. In this approach, the UAV can be modelled as an agent that interacts with an environment (the wireless network) over a sequence of discrete time steps. At each time step, the agent observes the current state of the environment and takes an action based on its current policy. The policy is a mapping from states to actions, which the agent learns through trial-and-error interactions with the environment. The goal of the agent is to learn the optimal policy that maximizes a reward function, which measures the quality of the agent's decisions. Compared to the convectional approach, the proposed architecture can greatly enhance network performance and potentially open a variety of UAV-assisted wireless applications.

Keywords: *Optimization, resource allocation, deep reinforcement learning, reward, user association*

■ ICEMIT IT119

AI-Powered Customer Profiling and Segmentation to Reduce Booking Cancellations

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Booking cancellations in industries such as travel, hospitality, and e-commerce present significant challenges by reducing revenue and disrupting operations. This research investigates the application of AI-powered customer profiling and segmentation to predict and reduce booking cancellations. Using survey data collected through Google Forms, key attributes like booking frequency, payment preferences, discount usage, and customer satisfaction are analyzed. The goal is to identify patterns that lead to cancellations and segment customers based on behavior and demographics.

Machine learning algorithms, including K-means clustering, Random Forest, and SVM, are used to create customer profiles and predict the likelihood of cancellations. Segmentation enables businesses to offer personalized interventions, such as discounts and reminders, targeted at customers with higher cancellation probabilities. Additionally, the study highlights how factors like price sensitivity, refund policies, and platform loyalty

influence cancellations, offering actionable insights to businesses. The results demonstrate that AI-driven segmentation and predictive modelling allow for more effective customer retention strategies, reducing cancellation rates while enhancing satisfaction. Personalized offers tailored to specific customer profiles foster long-term loyalty and improve overall booking retention. This research contributes to the field of AI applications in customer management by offering a framework that helps businesses proactively manage booking behaviors. Future work could explore the integration of real-time data and reinforcement learning to optimize the model further, providing even greater value to industries focused on online bookings and customer retention.

Keywords: *AI-Powered Customer Profiling, Booking Cancellations, Machine Learning, Customer Segmentation, Predictive Modelling.*

■ ICEMIT IT123

Molecular Pathogenesis and Epidemiological Dynamics of Cervical Neoplasia: Advances in Precision Diagnostics and Multimodal Therapeutics

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Due to restricted access to reasonably priced diagnostics and specialized care, cervical cancer is one of the main causes of death for women, with the majority of deaths taking place in low-resource settings. A low-cost, multiscale in vivo optical imaging system that combines portable colposcopy and high-resolution endomicroscopy (HRME) and is backed by a multiscale imaging fusion network (MSFN) for real-time detection of high-grade cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN 2+) is used in this study to address these issues. Furthermore, to improve the early diagnosis of cervical dysplasia, a multi-modal contrastive learning framework integrates textual data and colposcopic images utilizing sophisticated deep learning methods, such as CNN-based Variational Autoencoders (VAE). Machine learning techniques uncover important clinical and demographic risk variables using the UCI cervical cancer risk factors dataset; a Random Forest classifier achieves 99.36% accuracy in cervical cancer risk prediction.

With an emphasis on multi-stage severity assessments and mobile or web-based diagnostic tools, these developments provide scalable, resource-efficient solutions.

Keywords: Cervical cancer, cervical dysplasia, multiscale imaging, contrastive learning, computer-aided diagnosis, machine learning, cervical cancer risk prediction

■ ICEMIT IT127

Thermal Imaging and Machine Learning: Enhancing Night-time Pedestrian Detection for Autonomous Vehicles

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The purpose of this paper is to explore the potential of thermal imaging and machine learning

in improving safety of autonomous vehicles operating at night by enhancing their ability to detect pedestrians. Driving at night poses considerable challenges due to poor visibility which

heightens risks of accidents. The traditional cameras and sensors are often ineffective under such conditions; however, the use of thermal cameras that sense heat offers a promising way out. These devices can see pedestrians even in the dark because they produce heat. This review

examines present thermal imaging technology as well as various machine learning techniques

that analyse these images for accurate pedestrian detection It also investigates advantages and

disadvantages while using these technologies in self-driving cars. Despite of some impediments like high costs and need for high powered computers, there is a great promise for

nocturnal driving through combining thermal imaging with machine learning technologies.

Keywords: *Thermal Imaging, Machine Learning (ML), Autonomous Vehicles, You Only Look Once (YOLO), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Pedestrian Detection*

ICEMIT IT129

Intelligent Biodegradable Materials Composite Packaging (IBCP): An Integrated IoT-ML-LLM Approach for Sustainable Design, Tracking, and Waste Management

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Intelligent Biodegradable Composite Packaging (IBCP) integrates Internet of Things (IoT), Machine Learning (ML), and Large Language Models (LLM) for sustainable design, tracking, and waste management, addressing the critical need for eco-friendly packaging solutions. By combining biodegradable composite materials (natural fibers, bioplastics, biomass) with IoT sensors for real-time monitoring and ML algorithms for predictive maintenance and optimization, IBCP reduces material waste, enhances product shelf life, and promotes data-driven decision-making. LLM-driven Natural Language Processing (NLP) provides design recommendations, material selection guidance, and waste management advice, ensuring seamless integration with existing waste management systems. This innovative framework contributes to circular economy development, mitigates environmental impact from packaging waste, increases adoption of biodegradable materials, and improves supply chain efficiency. (Keywords: Sustainable Packaging, Biodegradable Composite Materials, IoT, Machine Learning, Large Language Models, Waste Management, Circular Economy, Eco-Friendly Packaging, Green Technology, Supply Chain Optimization).

Keywords: *Large Language Models, Natural Language Processing, Supply Chain Optimization*

■ ICEMIT IT131

Importance of Information Technology in Education in Uttarakhand

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Information Technology plays an important role in our lives. With the period, it made advancement in technology by making improvement in old technologies and introducing new technologies, applications and software. With the help of IT, India has developed a lot. Information technology is the technology which manages data, includes ways to collect, store, secure and share data, also involves tasks which are performed with the help of hardware and software. At modern times, Information Technology has become an integral part of wide range of business and commerce. It is also helpful in studying structures, procedures, and processing of various types of data. With the help of information technology, there is an improvement in daily life, career building through digital training.

It is playing a major role in making our work easy by improving communication standards and management of data. It also keeps our data and system safe and secure by ensuring its privacy. It has also expanded in sharing, social networking, connections, and communication.

In the field of career opportunities, there is a progress that is seen in business and commerce, all industries run with the help of technology which helps in expanding their business worldwide. With the help of IT, jobs are performed online sitting at home, finding jobs has also become easier,

jobs can be done world-wide in various companies and fields through the help of IT. IT has become major source of job and business expansion. The influence of IT emphasized on all sectors of society which enabled automation, data processing, and analysis, development in business communication and increase in efficiency and productivity. In the field of education, it provides mechanisms for e-learning and expands the provision of learning. In health care, it also helps in keeping patients records and providing diagnostic tools. With the help of IT, there is transparency in everything. It promotes communication and alliance with within or other organization. There is a full team who work through email, video conferencing, instant messaging and collaborative software platforms. In business management, helps in running business smoothly and gets involved easily in the market changes. IT helps in providing educational sources like online data base, e-learning through which educational opportunities broaden. It makes every work innovative and productive. It enhances and develops tools for computer-aided design, 3D modelling and simulation. IT manages to establish customer development retention by tracking customer behavior, preference and feedback. IT provides various services like Network services, compute services, Data Storage services, cyber security services, technical support services, cloud services, IT consulting services, and software development services.

■ ICEMIT IT132

Improving Accuracy of Marine Data Prediction using Hyper Parameters Optimisation of Hybrid Deep RNN

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Climatic changes and anthropogenic disturbances are considered as one of the threats to continued existence of tropical marine ecosystem such as coral reefs and fish assemblages. These threats are complex in nature and time variant in type thus, posing a significant challenge in prediction of marine benthics. Moreover, to achieve at improved accuracy of predictions, an advanced predictive model and optimisation of its hyper parameters is required. Accurate predictions are essentially required for informed decision making towards marine data protection, thus leading to safeguarding life below water which is the 14th Sustainable Development Goal of United Nations. This research aimed to predict the marine benthics of Flic en Flac lagoon of Republic of Mauritius. The prediction involved independent variables namely Sea Surface Temperature (SST), pH, Practical Salinity (PSU), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD), Nitrate- Nitrogen contents, and Phosphate measured in the lagoon waters. The target variables are Hard Corals (HC), and Fish

assemblages. This research proposes Self Organizing Maps (SOM) clustered Deep Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), called the hybrid model (SOM Deep RNN) for high quality predictions. The research further aimed to improve the prediction accuracy of SOM Deep RNN by optimising SOM and Deep RNN hyper parameters using methods namely grid search, random search, and Bayesian optimisation. The HPO methods for Deep RNN were compared based on the evaluation metrics such as Root Mean square Error, Mean Absolute Error and R-squared score. As an outcome of this comparison, the research determined that random search is the best hyper parameters optimisation method for SOM clustering and grid search is the best hyper parameters optimisation method for Deep RNN prediction model for the marine data under consideration.

Keywords: Bayesian Optimization, grid search, deep recurrent neural network, marine data prediction, Mauritius, optimization of hyper parameters, prediction, random search, self-organizing maps.

■ ICEMIT IT133

Analysis of Remote Voting System Mechanism

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This study investigates several remote voting approaches, discussing behavior-based evolution of the models and security over them. This paper presents key properties of Helios, Scantegrity and Pretty Good Democracy while discussing their impact on verifiability, integrity undermining privacy penetration resistance. Further, the paper presents a comprehensive study of such established studies, discussing key findings from these works to provide perspective on the issues and trajectories within remote voting technologies. It identifies a continued requirement for easily used, verifiable platforms that scale whilst maintaining confidence in them. This paper demonstrates the necessity of continuous evolution in both cryptographic protocols and usability design for solving remaining problems with remote voting systems.

■ ICEMIT IT134

A Novel Multi-Estimator Framework for Sequential Forward Feature Selection in Cancer Prediction

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Cancer continues to be a major global health challenge, standing as one of the leading causes of death around the world. Early and accurate prediction is essential for effective diagnosis and treatment, ultimately improving patient survival rates. In recent years, machine learning techniques have emerged as powerful tools for disease prediction. Cancer prediction is challenging due to the disease's complexity and heterogeneity, highlighting the need for effective feature selection methods. This process is essential for enhancing model performance by reducing dimensionality and improving interpretability. However, relying on a single estimator for feature selection may not capture all relevant patterns in the data, potentially limiting the model's predictive capabilities.

This study proposes a novel multi-estimator framework employing Sequential Forward Feature

Selection (SFS) to optimize feature subsets for breast cancer prediction. The proposed method

employs multiple estimators like Logistic Regression (LR), Naïve Bayes (NB), Support Vector

Machine (SVM), and Decision Tree to identify the most significant feature subset for each model. By considering the unique perspectives of different algorithms, the approach aims to enhance overall classification performance.

The framework utilizes the Wisconsin Breast Cancer Dataset (WBCD) from the UCI Machine Learning Repository. The WBCD is

highly imbalanced; hence, the Synthetic Minority Over-Sampling Technique (SMOTE) was applied for class balancing, followed by standard scaling for normalization. Experimental results clearly demonstrate that SFS with LR, NB, SVM, and DT methods selected 9,10,15 and 18 features to find optimal solution. Although SVM had the highest accuracy i.e. 97.90%, LR with 97.72% accuracy was preferred for its simplicity, interpretability, and efficient use of fewer features.

Applying the selected features, the optimized LR model achieved an accuracy of 97.90%, precision of 97.33%, recall of 98.60%, and an AUC of 99.85%, outperforming NB and closely rivaling the complex SVM model. Additionally, an ANN attained slightly higher accuracy at 98.60%, but the LR model offered comparable performance with significant advantages in simplicity and computational efficiency.

The findings definitively demonstrate that the proposed multi-estimator framework substantially enhances the classification performance of simpler models through effective feature selection. By rigorously assessing the importance of variables across various algorithms, the study clearly establishes that even basic models, like logistic regression (LR), can achieve impressive predictive accuracy, making them formidable alternatives to complex models in breast cancer prediction.

Keywords: *Sequential Forward Feature Selection, SMOTE, GridSearch, Breast Cancer, Disease Prediction.*

■ ICEMIT IT135

Combining Mathematical Epidemiology and Machine Learning for Disease Spread Analysis

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The Susceptible-Infected-Recovered (SIR) model is a cornerstone in epidemiological modelling used to predict the spread of infectious diseases. With the emergence of machine learning (ML), combining these technologies has shown considerable potential in enhancing the predictive accuracy and adaptability of the SIR model. This paper reviews the integration of the SIR model with machine learning, focusing on methodologies, applications, advancements, and challenges in improving disease outbreak predictions.

Keywords: *SIR model, machine learning, hybrid models, epidemiological modelling*

■ ICEMIT IT136

Forecasting Hospital Readmission Rates in the U.S. Using Time-Series Analysis and Machine Learning Models.

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Hospital readmissions pose significant challenges to the healthcare system in the United States, impacting patient well-being and leading to financial penalties for hospitals. This research aims to develop a predictive framework for forecasting hospital readmission rates using a combination of time-series models and machine learning techniques. The study leverages datasets such as the CMS Hospital Readmission Reduction Program and HCUP, focusing on key variables including patient demographics, medical history, length of stay, and comorbidities. Models such as ARIMA, LSTM, and XG-Boost are employed to capture temporal patterns and complex relationships within the data. Additionally, SHAP analysis is used to explain the key drivers influencing predictions. Simulations of various healthcare policies, such as follow-up care

and reduced hospital stays, are conducted to assess their impact on readmission rates. The results aim to offer actionable insights for healthcare providers, enabling targeted interventions to reduce readmission rates and improve patient outcomes. This study emphasizes the use of data-driven methodologies for effective healthcare delivery, aiming to balance predictive accuracy and model interpretability through the integration of explainable AI techniques.

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